

building-integrated user-
empowered flexibility trading

Deliverable D3.1: Description of the preliminary multi- carrier flexibility services for buildings

WP3 – Flexibility Extraction Services

March 31, 2026

PUBLIC

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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the preliminary technical developments of Work Package 3 (WP3) within the BlueBird project, focusing on the extraction, optimisation, and market integration of multi-carrier flexibility from buildings. WP3 provides the core decision-making intelligence that enables buildings to respond optimally to energy prices, forecasts, and flexibility market opportunities while respecting comfort and operational constraints.

The document describes the modelling framework, digital twin approach, forecasting services, and optimisation methodologies developed to support sequential decision-making under uncertainty. Special emphasis is placed on Model Predictive Control and reinforcement learning-based solutions, which allow buildings to anticipate future conditions and act proactively. An illustrative example based on the Montcada multi-zone building demonstrates how economic MPC can be extended to robustly participate in capacity markets.

The results presented in this deliverable constitute the first integrated version of the WP3 technical stack. They establish a solid foundation for further refinement, large-scale validation, and extension toward more advanced uncertainty-aware and data-driven control strategies in the final version (D3.2).

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Table I. Acronyms and Definitions

Acronym	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interfaces
BMS	Building Management System
D	Deliverable
DT	Digital Twin
E	Estimated
EC	European Commission
FM	Flexibility Manager
GPU	Graphics Processing Units
ICT	Information & Communication Tools
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LP	Linear Programming
M	Measured
MD	Multiple Dispatch
MDP	Markov Decision Process
MILP	Mixed-Integer Linear Programming
ML	Machine Learning
MLP	Multilayer Perceptron
MPC	Model Predictive Control
MS	Milestones
RL	Reinforcement Learning
RMPC	Robust Model Predictive Control
TM	Trading Manager
WP	Work Package

I. INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this deliverable is to document the preliminary technical outcomes of WP3, which is responsible for enabling buildings to act as flexible, market-aware energy assets within the BlueBird framework. WP3 bridges the gap between physical building systems and energy markets by combining digital twins, forecasting services, and advanced optimisation techniques.

Within WP3, buildings are modelled as controlled dynamical systems whose internal states (e.g., zone temperatures or energy storage levels) evolve in response to control actions and external disturbances such as weather conditions. Due to partial knowledge of the physical processes and the need for modularity and scalability, building dynamics are represented using a grey-box modelling approach, where physically meaningful structures are retained while unknown parameters are identified using data-driven learning methods. These models are encapsulated within the Digital Twin.

The operation of the building is formulated as an optimal control problem, cast in a sequential decision-making framework under uncertainty. At each decision step, control actions are computed by solving a constrained optimisation problem over a finite prediction horizon. The objective is to minimise operational costs and maximise flexibility revenues while ensuring comfort, safety, and technical constraints are respected under uncertain future conditions.

In addition to optimisation-based control, WP3 also explores Reinforcement Learning (RL) approaches for specific asset classes such as electric vehicle charging and battery systems. In these cases, RL is used as an alternative control paradigm to learn operational policies directly from data and interaction, complementing the model-based methods used for building thermal control.

This deliverable provides a structured description of the adopted modelling approach, the supporting digital twin and forecasting infrastructure, and the optimisation methods implemented in the Flexibility Manager. It also outlines how these components interact with market-oriented modules, referred to as the Trading Manager.

II. POSITION OF WP3 WITHIN BLUE BIRD

The BlueBird project aims to transform buildings from passive energy consumers into active, intelligent participants in modern energy systems by enabling their adoption as competitive energy flexibility assets. To achieve this, BlueBird delivers a comprehensive, validated toolset that supports both the optimisation of building energy performance and the provision of flexibility services in energy markets. The project is explicitly designed to ensure smooth integration with energy system stakeholders, such as Transmission System Operators (TSOs), Distribution System Operators (DSOs), and aggregators, while simultaneously addressing the needs, constraints, and acceptance criteria of end users, including building managers and occupants.

A core objective of BlueBird is to enable any type of building to optimise its internal operation and flexibility in response to dynamic external conditions. This actuation includes responding to energy price signals and leveraging integration across connected building systems, including HVAC, energy storage, renewable energy sources, district heating, geothermal installations, and gas-based systems. These optimisation strategies also account for contextual information, including weather conditions, traffic patterns, air quality, and building usage profiles, ensuring flexibility without compromising comfort, safety, or operational constraints.

For this purpose, a set of tools has been designed to create a modular system that can accommodate all these buildings and asset types by changing only the required module. Moreover, not all buildings or assets require all services; therefore, with this approach, only the modules required for the specific service need to be installed. The relation between the modules is indicated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Modules diagram (from BlueBird deliverable 6.1)

As shown in the previous figure, WP3 tasks play a central role in this architecture. The modules developed within this WP are:

- Forecasting (T3.1), which is in charge of providing the forecast of exogenous variables to the DT to make the necessary predictions of the required scenarios.
- Digital Twin (T3.5), whose role is to encapsulate the building or asset dynamics to determine how they will react to different actuations.
- Flexibility Manager (T3.3) is in charge of communicating with the Trading Manager, operating the Flexibility Manager Optimisation (T3.4), and communicating the optimisation results to the building assets for direct actuation (T6.3) or to the required user interaction tool (T4.3) for users to actuate in the building.
- Bidding optimisation (T3.2) is a module designed to optimise bidding in the case of interacting with capacity markets.

III. TECHNICAL DESCRIPTION OF MULTI-CARRIER FLEXIBILITY SERVICES

III.1. BlueBird WP3 Service Overview

The purpose of WP3 is to develop the technical layer of the project's flexibility services. After close and repeated interaction with the pilot partners, the nature of each pilot's needs and flexibility capabilities has been identified and defined technically.

BlueBird's technical solution instantiates a framework for sequential decision-making under uncertainty. The framework itself is generic enough to accommodate different cases and different energy carriers, each instantiation is tailored to the specifics of each pilot.

III.2. BlueBird Data-Driven Models for Buildings and Assets

III.2.1. Modelling approach

The modelling approach is based on state-space modelling and Markov Decision Processes, defined as:

- 1) Temporal Granularity: the frequency with which decisions need to be made gives rise to a discrete set $\mathcal{T} = \{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$
- 2) State Variables $\mathbf{x}_t = (x_{i,t})_{i \in I}$: for each $t \in \mathcal{T}$, the state variables jointly constitute the necessary and sufficient information to capture the current conditions of the system, comprehensively enough so that the system's evolution is probabilistically predictable.
- 3) Action Variables $\mathbf{u}_t = (u_{j,t})_{j \in J}$: for each $t \in \mathcal{T}$, the action variables constitute the control knobs of the system, i.e. what decisions does the BlueBird solution get to control.
- 4) Cost Function $C(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{u}_t)$: the cost function maps a given state-action pair (i.e. system conditions and chosen actions) to a perceived cost, the units of which can be different depending on each case's objectives.
- 5) Transition Dynamics $D(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{u}_t; \psi)$: the transition function maps a given state-action pair to the state in which the system is expected to transition next, as in: $\mathbf{x}_{t+1} = D(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{u}_t; \psi)$, where ψ denotes the parameters governing the randomness inherent to the system evolution.

The solution concept takes the form of a decision-making policy π , which maps any state in which the system can find itself to a prescribed action, as in: $\mathbf{u}_t = \pi(\mathbf{x}_t)$. Thereby, the problem of designing a decision-making framework for a pilot takes the form of designing a decision-making policy, i.e. a method for making a decision \mathbf{u}_t on the control actions, at each time t , given the updated information \mathbf{x}_t received from the real system. The objective is to make "smart" decisions, in the sense that the algorithm anticipates the evolution of the system in future timeslots and minimizes the system's expected cost over the entire horizon, i.e., including immediate costs *and* expected future costs. Formally, the design problem takes the form:

$$\min_{\pi} \left\{ \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} E_{\xi \sim \pi} [C(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{u}_t)] \right\}$$

Subject to:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u}_t &= \pi(\mathbf{x}_t) \\ \mathbf{x}_{t+1} &= D(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{u}_t; \psi) \\ \mathbf{u}_t &\in \mathcal{U} \\ \mathbf{x}_t &\in \mathcal{X} \end{aligned}$$

where the expectation is over the system's trajectories $\xi = (\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{u}_t)_{t \in \mathcal{T}}$ conditioned over the decision-making policy π . The sets \mathcal{U} and \mathcal{X} define the feasible domains of actions and states respectively, instantiating e.g. equipment limits, comfort limits, etc.

Importantly, the evolution of some of the state variables is independent of the chosen actions (think, e.g. weather variables, electricity prices, etc). We thereby distinguish between *exogenous* state variables $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_t$, for which $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{t+1} = D(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_t; \psi)$, and *endogenous* state variables $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_t$ for which $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{t+1} = D(\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_t, \mathbf{u}_t; \psi)$. This allows us to split the methodology of designing a well-performing policy π , into three Tasks:

- a) Developing a Digital Twin of the system: the Digital Twin (DT) undertakes the role of instantiating the transition function D for *endogenous* state variables $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_t$, i.e. predicting the evolution of the system from any given state and chosen action to the next state, one step into the future (note that a multi-step prediction can be made by using the function D recursively).
- b) Developing Forecast Services to predict the evolution of *exogenous* state variables $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_t$.
- c) Developing an optimization algorithm that incorporates
 - i. the prediction of *exogenous* state variables $(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_t)_{t \in H}$ for a lookahead horizon H , and
 - ii. the state transition dynamics D for *endogenous* state variables,
 and prescribes the decisions that minimize the expected system cost for the lookahead horizon.

The full methodological background of our approach is detailed in [Tsaousoglou2026]. The developments for each of these three Tasks are elaborated below.

III.2.2. Digital Twin Framework

The concept of a considered digital twin framework is used to manage the control and digital representation of the state and environment of devices. Digital twins are used to manage, predict, and control the behaviour of real-world systems. To encompass the entire framework, the following components are integrated:

1. The device that exists in the real world, such as a building or an industrial system, that is aimed to be controlled and its corresponding actuation effects in the building.
2. A virtual representation of the building asset that is aimed to be controlled and its corresponding actuation effects in the building. Therefore, the modelling of these assets and the corresponding effects of their control.
3. The possible actuation that can be controlled within the optimisation procedure.

To accurately represent the real-world environment, the model must have the proper context. A context model can abstract the real world while retaining relevant information, such as location and dependencies between system components. The digital twin is the coupling of the models with their context. Therefore, the digital twin can simulate how the system will behave in future scenarios, which can then be used to optimise control.

The identified four relevant components for such a framework:

- The data from the building asset and its environment relevant to the control. Using this information, the models can abstract the device's response and its effects on the control signals. The data stores all relevant information describing the asset's physical reaction and its environment.
- The models: to that end, we identified two main components required to represent a digital twin. First, a digital representation of the device, a model of what is aimed to be controlled, including all behavioural reactions and dependencies. Second, the real-world effects model and interactions with its environment. Context metadata is needed to support identification and environmental considerations. The acceptance constraints need to be considered, which can be defined by the end user of the system.

- The optimisation: This component leverages the digital twin's models to solve a mathematical optimization problem. The framework evaluates the feasible state space to determine an optimal control strategy. By minimizing a defined cost function, such as energy consumption or operational delay, subject to system dynamics and physical constraints, the system generates the most efficient control actions for the physical asset. A Two-Way Communication path is needed between the real world and the models. First, it is required to obtain information about the actual state of the device and its environment. Second, a communication back to the controlled asset is required to send the actuator setpoints.

III.2.3. Training interface

The training interface of the digital twin environment takes the digital twin context model to create a simulation model. The flexibility manager needs the simulation model in a linearised way. This linear model is comprised of three parts: First, the state in which the information is contained, which we want to predict. Second, the control variables which, are the parameters that we can optimise. Finally, the third term represents some error that stems, for example, from data inaccuracies. The training interface maps all properties that are marked as dependent to the first term and all controllable and non-controllable properties that are marked as independent to the second term. With that done, a standard linear regression solver can be used to learn the relevant coefficients that are used by the flexibility manager.

III.2.4. Runtime interface

The runtime interface provides the learned coefficients for the flexibility manager. It acts as the operational bridge between the learned models and the live control system. Its primary role is to provide the flexibility manager with the necessary computational assets to execute real-time decision-making. Specifically, the interface serves two critical functions:

- Model Parameter Provision: It delivers the learned coefficients of the system dynamics—such as state-space matrices—required by the optimization solver to predict future states based on current inputs.
- System Evolution Forecasting: Beyond static coefficients, the interface can generate real-time forecasts of the system's evolution. These trajectories allow the flexibility manager to validate control strategies against expected behaviour and perform internal simulations to ensure that the proposed setpoints remain within safe operational bounds before deployment.

III.2.5. Example – Energy consumption optimisation of Multi zone building-Casa de la Vila (Montcada)

The digital twin pipeline and modelling approach is presented in Annex I: Digital Twin definition for Multi-zone building. All the associated development is uploaded into the GitHub repository:

<https://github.com/BlueBird-project/flexibility-manager/tree/main/dt/BlueBird-multizone-modelling/BC2%20-%20Montcada%20building>

III.3. Forecasting Modules

The purpose of this section is to list all the procedures that will be developed or implemented to ensure a steady flow of predictions for the necessary variables in the system. This list is a generic description, as some procedures are not input-locked, meaning the modules may vary based on the information available.

However, new information, such as new variables, will be examined and either accepted or rejected in a semi-automatic way.

Within the forecasting modules there are two sets of functionalities, depending on when a new, specific model is trained or not for the results.

III.3.1. Forecasting Services

All results here come from services that fall outside of the developments of the BlueBird project. Mainly this has to do with generic weather forecasting, for which no additional models will be trained. This is due to the availability of already existing services which have much more accurate weather-related data than what BlueBird pilots might have available. However, if there is a possibility to use pilot's data for it, this will be prioritized over services data as forecast results.

These services may include information that is not forecasting but future values such as price values for future's markets.

III.3.2. Forecasting Engine

This is the core of the developments for the forecasting module. It follows previous results and methodologies. There are three core entities in the forecasting engine:

- **FAST Methodology.** It is a four-component methodology to standardize AI procedures, mostly training and forecasting based on the main activities necessary. These components allow customization of the procedure without the need to change the pipelines. The pipelines are therefore designed to work with these components in mind. In these components we find a) data management (Forge), model training (Augur), model metrics (Surveil) and model forecasting and explainability (Translate).

Figure 2. FAST methodology to standardize AI procedures

- **Pipelines.** For the forecasting engine there are three main pipelines:
 - a) *Training* which extracts the available data, processes it, trains one or several AI models and saves the results of this effort,
 - b) *Inference*, which takes an existing model (usually the one with the best scores) and produces the forecasts for the necessary variables,
 - c) *Metrics*, in which the forecasts are checked against the real values and based on the variance of the new data the decision is made whether to train a new model and which set of values will be used.

- **Algorithms.** There is already a wide set of algorithms for some of the components of the methodology already tested and validated. This includes algorithms like Prophet or NHITS, processing procedures like anomaly detection or interpolation, and custom metrics like SMAPE or Coverage, with specific regards to Time Series Analysis.

The system will allow to train and process the data as the user or users intend as well as explore and investigate the data as much as possible but there will be two considerations that will be included to guide the experience towards a set of behavioural patterns.

- Explainability. In automatic mode, the system will go from simpler models to more complex ones, only going to a more complex one if the previously trained does not meet the necessary evaluations. This allows the system to retain explainability as much as possible, i.e., showing what variables were more important and how in the final forecast.
- Energy consumption. There will an energy evaluation of training and inference. This is so that the system also checks the most energy efficient procedure to train and forecast. Metrics will be designed and based on previous training runs the hyperparameters will be changed to ensure the energy consumed in the AI procedures is reduced. This also goes alongside the explainability side. Usually complex models such as Transformers, MLP, required not only specific hardware such as GPUs, but also are more energy taxing, so staying with simpler models also reduces consumption.

An example of these FAST Objects is provided in the GitHub repository:

<https://github.com/BlueBird-project/flexibility-manager/tree/main/forecasting>

III.3.3. Forecasting Procedure

In this subsection, the procedure and architecture behind the implementation of the pipelines will be explained.

Figure 3. Forecasting scheme procedure

The core of the forecasting resides in 4 elements that work in tandem:

- FAST Pipelines. As explained before, this is the core code that allows you to train, forecast and review the models.
- SQLite Database. All the results are stored internally in an SQLite database. This database has a particular format and schema that ensure replication and ease of use. This DB hosts raw, real data as well as all the exogenous variables necessary to train or process and the forecasts.

Figure 4. Data scheme in the forecasting module

3. Prefect Server. The pipelines run using a prefect server. Prefect is a python library to allow orchestration fully using python as a code base. Deployments can be set to download data daily, train sequentially or inference. The pipelines are fixed for training, inference and review pipelines, and there will be guides to download data using the same code base as the rest of the FAST Pipelines.
4. NOVA UI. Alongside the code, there is a dashboard created in Streamlit which shows the status of the data and the pipeline execution. There is also the possibility to execute pipelines directly from the UI.

Figure 5. Forecasting visualisation

III.3.3.a. Use of Forecasting

This architecture is already in place at the internal servers of Inetum, but a local deployment will be available to create training servers for forecasting. To train models for forecasting, it is recommended to install hardware with GPUs and High RAM memory. Some of the tests running use NeuralForecast which is a python library that can be accelerated through CUDA, this allows to reduce the timing it takes to train and forecast, that way you can set up a high degree of excellency for the models as they can be retrained frequently.

This allows three main ways to use the forecasting engine:

- a) In-house training and in-house inference. Using a static or dynamic data table, an initial version of the model is trained. Once this is ready, the inference begins. The values will be allocated into a middleware Cloud DB that allows pilots to access and write data into it. This way the pilots upload real values which are then stored in-house at Inetum, and with this the review and retrain pipelines are executed if necessary.
- b) In-house training and local inference. Using a static data table, the model is trained as the previous method, but then the model is delivered through a documented API that the pilots can execute locally. The only way to update the model this way is through a new in-house manual execution.

Figure 6. FastAPI swagger visualisation

- c) Local training and inference. Locally, pilots use training and inference using the pipelines provided.

All the information of the use can be found in the README [for the forecasting engine](#).

III.4. Flexibility Manager

III.4.1. Model Predictive Control

The purpose of this module is to return a decision \mathbf{u}_t , at each point in time, given the updated system state \mathbf{x}_t . The Model Predictive Control (MPC) module, sets a lookahead horizon H and incorporates the future predictions for the exogenous variables $(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_t)_{t \in H}$ and the linearized dynamics $\tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{t+1} = D(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{u}_t; \psi)$ for the endogenous state variables, and solves the following Mixed Integer Linear Program (MILP):

$$\min_V \left\{ \sum_{t \in H} C(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{u}_t) \right\}$$

Subject to:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_{t+1} &= D(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{u}_t; \psi), \quad \forall t \in H \\ (\hat{\mathbf{x}}_t)_{t \in H} &\sim \text{given/forecasted} \\ \mathbf{u}_t &\in \mathcal{U} \\ \mathbf{x}_t &\in \mathcal{X} \end{aligned}$$

where the optimization variables are $V = (\mathbf{u}_t, \tilde{\mathbf{x}}_t)_{t \in H}$. While the actions $(\mathbf{u}_\tau)_{\tau \in [t+1, H]}$ referring to the future are only *prospective*, the actions \mathbf{u}_t for the current time t are *effective*, i.e. they are returned to be applied in the real system. The whole process repeats at the next hour, using the updated state information, which is possibly different from the previously predicted one, thereby allowing MPC to update its previous prospective decisions for a given time into the corrected effective decisions.

Continuing with the Casa de la Vila Barcelona Montcada example describing the operation optimization based on the ToU electricity price. The code and documentation are available here: <https://github.com/BlueBird-project/flexibility-manager/tree/main/FlexOPTi>.

III.4.2. Reinforcement Learning

The idea of Reinforcement Learning (RL) in this project is to control a specific asset with data-driven techniques, being able to recognize some patterns and exploiting flexibility.

A Reinforcement Learning algorithm is composed by an agent that interacts with a specific environment, to maximize a reward. This reward is telling how “good” our agent is doing.

In general, the agent observes a state s_t at a specific time t . The agent will make an action a_t based on the actual state, and it will be executed on the environment, which will give back a reward r_t , and then transition to a new state s_{t+1} . The main goal of a RL algorithm is to learn a good policy $\pi(a|s)$, (policy of choosing the action given a specific state) i.e., the good behavior, able to choose the best action to maximize the expected cumulative reward over a specific time window. More into specific, the cumulative reward is defined by this formula:

$$J(\pi) = E_{\pi}[\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \gamma^t r_t],$$

Which means the value we expect by following a policy π , by summing up all the rewards over time. Those rewards are multiplied by a discount factor γ , which tells us how “far” we are looking in the future (the more this value is close to 1, the more we care about future actions and states; the more is close to 0, the more we give importance to immediate steps).

Now, the importance of an action following a policy is given by its action value, also called Q-function, which is telling through the cumulative reward how good is the chosen action in a specific state:

$$Q^{\pi}(s, a) = E_{\pi}[\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \gamma^k r_{t+k} | s_t = s, a_t = a]$$

The Bellman equation, which is the most important equation for a RL algorithm, shows us the recursive relationship between the actual reward plus all future rewards, by applying the same policy:

$$Q^{\pi}(s, a) = E[r_t | \gamma Q^{\pi}(s', a')],$$

and this equation is used for updating the estimation of our algorithm. RL is learning with a trial-and-error mode, by exploring new states with new action and remembering the previous best actions.

In our case, RL is used for Electric Vehicle (EV) charging problem, by controlling EV chargers and deciding whether is the right moment for charging. The actions, in fact, can be idle or charge for each charger, and, for a cost-minimization problem, the reward at a given time t is:

$$r_t = p_{1,t} + p_{2,t}$$

This reward is composed by two elements: $p_{1,t}$ is the cost of purchasing a certain amount of electricity at a given time, while $p_{2,t}$ is the penalty applied when an EV is not at the desired charge.

Those two values are usually negative, and the goal is receiving as less penalty as possible.

This is applied for all EVs, and the RL agent is trained with some historical data to learn patterns and charge EVs at the lowest costs, while hopefully charging all vehicles.

An example of a simple RL application can be seen with the EWH case (BC7), where a charging station with four chargers is delivering electricity to the connected vehicles. The agent will choose whether to charge or idle, with respect to the price, varying per-time (TOU price or Real time price).

The implementation of the algorithm and a more in-depth documentation is provided here: https://github.com/BlueBird-project/flexibility-manager/tree/main/dt/EWH_EV_charging_BC7.

III.5. The Trading Manager

III.5.1. Trading Integration

A detail description of the Trading Manager (TM) is given in D5.1.

The interface between the Flexibility Manager (FM) and the Trading Manager will be implemented using the Knowledge Engine (KE). The Knowledge Engine will act as a standardised (based on SAREF ontology), and interoperable data exchange layer, enabling structured communication between FM and TM across different energy market contexts.

Figure 7. Flexibility Manager and Trading Manager interaction interface

We foresee two complementary interaction approaches, depending on the target market:

1. Capacity Market–oriented interaction

In the context of the Capacity Market, the FM will initiate the communication by sending a request to the TM via the Knowledge Engine. This request will include:

- The time horizon for which energy price and optimisation information is required,
- The energy production function,
- The energy consumption function,
- The function describing additional operational or flexibility-related costs.

Based on this input, the TM will perform an optimisation analysis, taking into account market conditions and constraints, and will respond with the optimal solution for each time unit within the requested time window. This response may include recommended production and consumption levels, as well as corresponding price signals, enabling the FM to make informed operational decisions.

Figure 8. Flexibility Manager and Trading Manager information exchange operating in capacity markets

2. Interaction for other energy markets

For all other energy markets (e.g. day-ahead, intraday, balancing, or local flexibility markets), the interaction model is simpler.

In this case, the TM will provide the FM with:

- Energy prices for production and consumption,
- For a specific time period requested by the FM.

The TM will determine and return the best available prices by analysing the relevant energy markets and market segments applicable to the given time frame. No additional optimisation functions are exchanged in this scenario; the focus is on delivering accurate and timely market price information to support FM decision-making.

Figure 9. Flexibility Manager and Trading Manager information exchange operating in time of use markets

III.5.2. Example – BC2 Montcada

Following the Casa de la Vila Montcada example from BC2, the flexibility manager optimisation code can be found here: <https://github.com/BlueBird-project/flexibility-manager/tree/main/FlexOPTi>.

This example demonstrates the application of the WP3 methodology to the Montcada multi-zone building, with a focus on HVAC operations. It highlights participation in capacity markets as well as collaboration with the commercialisation agent to reduce energy costs by operating in both the day-ahead and intraday energy markets. The objective is to determine how much flexibility the building can reliably commit while ensuring occupant comfort and adhering to physical constraints.

The building is represented by a digital twin that tracks the evolution of indoor temperatures based on meteorological conditions at the building's location, the HVAC system settings for each room, and the thermal behaviour of adjoining spaces. These temperature data, along with external disturbances, are used to model the building's electrical power consumption. Detailed information about the Montcada building digital twin can be found in Annex I: Digital Twin definition for Multi-zone building, and is available in the GitHub repository: <https://github.com/BlueBird-project/flexibility-manager/tree/main/dt/BlueBird-multizone-modelling/BC2%20-%20Montcada%20building>.

Capacity provision is modelled as a deviation from a nominal consumption trajectory, responding to either upward or downward activation requests from the market. To ensure operational feasibility under uncertainty, we employ a Two-Stage Stochastic Programming approach.

The Flexibility Manager optimizes capacity commitments by partitioning the decision process into two distinct stages:

1. First-Stage Decisions (Here-and-Now): Conducted before market closure, the model determines the optimal capacity commitments for future time blocks. These decisions are made under uncertainty regarding the actual activation requests.
2. Second-Stage Decisions (Wait-and-See): These represent the "recourse" actions, the real-time adjustments to the building's consumption, taken after an activation request is realized.

IV. PILOTS INSTANTIATION

To ensure consistent formulation across the different pilots, variables used in the optimization framework are grouped into four categories: states, control inputs, exogenous states (also called disturbances), and algebraic variables.

Table 2. variables used in the optimization framework

Category	Symbol	Description	Source
State	x_k	System continuous state at time step k	Digital Twin
State	z_k	System binary state at time step k	Digital Twin
Control input	u_k	Control variables decided by the Flexibility Manager	Optimization (Flexibility Manager)
Disturbance	d_k	Exogenous inputs affecting system dynamics	Forecasting
Algebraic	y_k	Variables computed from the state and control	Digital Twin
Market parameters	Π_k	Market price signals	Trading Manager
Parameters	P	Metadata (constraints bounds, parameters, etc.)	Demo

The time index k denotes the control step in the discrete-time optimization horizon.

Variables shown in italics represent the decisions determined by the optimization process. In contrast, variables in straight text are fixed inputs provided by forecasts or pre-defined system parameters.

The model's linear constraints and binary variables allow it to be solved via standard open-source MILP software.

IV.1. Pilot Classification

The modelling process, ranging from digital twin development to final optimization, presents a unique challenge in the Blue Bird project due to the versatility of the pilots and their respective objectives in achieving flexibility. To streamline development, pilots are grouped into clusters where modelling logic and codebase can be shared.

Table 3. Demo site clustering by model framework

Model Framework	Pilot / Demo Sites
Room Temperature	AMB, ENEA, EWH
District Heating	Karno
Hydraulic	Enlion
EV	WeSmart, EWH

Table 4. Demo site clustering by objective

Objective	Pilot / Demo Sites
Minimize Electricity Price (ToU)	All
Access Intraday Market	AMB
Access Day-Ahead Market	AMB, EWH, Enlion, ENEA

IV.2. Pilot: AMB Montcada

IV.2.1. Sets and Indices

Table 5. Sets and Indices in Montcada building

Symbol	Description
\mathcal{R}	Set of rooms
$r \in \mathcal{R}$	Room index
$k = 0, \dots, H_u - 1$	Control step
H_u	MPC horizon length
Δt	Time step

IV.2.2. State Variable

Table 6. State variables in Montcada building

Symbol	Description
T_k^r	Room r temperature
T_k	Stacked vector of room temperatures
$a_k^r \in \{0,1\}$	HVAC r status. Binary. 1: HVAC ON, 0: HVAC OFF

IV.2.3. Control Variables

Table 7. Control variables in Montcada building

Symbol	Description
$T_k^{r,sp}$	Temperature setpoint for room r
T_k^{sp}	Stacked setpoints
$P_k^{PV,used}$	PV power used for self-consumption
$P_k^{PV,curt}$	PV power curtailed
P_k^\downarrow	Power bought from the grid

IV.2.4. Exogenous state - origin: Forecasting Service

Table 8. Exogenous states for forecasting service in Montcada building

Symbol	Description
T_k^{ext}	External air temperature
Φ_k	Stacked vector of room temperatures
V_k	Wind vector
P_k^{PV}	PV production
P_k^{rest}	Non-controlled building load

We define the stacked weather disturbances

$$d_k = \left[T_k^{ext \top} \quad \Phi_k^\top \quad V_k^\top \right]^\top$$

IV.2.5. Exogenous state - origin: Trading Manager

Table 9. Exogenous states for the trading manager in Montcada building

Symbol	Description
π_k^\downarrow	Electricity purchase price (ToU)

IV.2.6. Algebraic

Table 10. Algebraic symbols in Montcada building

Symbol	Description
p_k^r	HVAC electrical consumption of room r
p_k	Stacked HVAC power
$P_k = \sum_{r \in \mathcal{R}} p_k^r$	Total power used by the rooms

IV.2.7. Parameters (metadata)

Table 11. Parameters in Montcada building

Symbol	Description
\bar{B}	Grid purchase limits
\underline{T}^r	Room temperature lower bound
\bar{T}^r	Room temperature upper bound
\underline{P}	Power lower limit
\bar{P}	Power upper limit

IV.2.8. Digital Twin

The model of the room temperature follows an ARX linear structure.

$$T_k^r = \sum_{i=1}^N a_i T_{k-i}^r + \sum_{i=0}^M b_i T_{k-i}^{sp} + \sum_{i=0}^L c_i d_{k-i}$$

The total power consumed by the assets is obtain with a linear algebraic equation.

$$P_k = g(T_k, T_{k-1}, T_k^{sp}, d_k)$$

Both the state evolution (room temperature evolution) and power relation are described in detail in the appendix. Those enter as constraints in the Model Predictive Control optimization scheme.

IV.2.9. Model Predictive Control

The receding horizon optimization problem reads as

$$\underset{\substack{T^{sp}, T \\ a \\ p^{PV,used} \\ p^{PV,curt} \\ p^\downarrow}}{\text{minimize}} \sum_{k=0}^{H_u-1} P_k^\downarrow \pi_k^\downarrow \Delta t$$

subject to ($\forall k = 0, \dots, H_u - 1$)

Power balance constraints:

$$\begin{aligned} P_k^{PV,used} + P_k^{PV,curt} &= P_k^{PV} \\ P_k^\downarrow + P_k^{PV,used} &= P_k + P_k^{rest} \end{aligned}$$

Electrical constraints:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 \leq P_k^{PV,used} &\leq P_k^{PV} \\ 0 \leq P_k^{PV,curt} &\leq P_k^{PV} \\ 0 \leq P_k^\downarrow &\leq \bar{B} \end{aligned}$$

Comfort and Power constraints:

$$\begin{aligned} \underline{T}^r \leq T_k^r &\leq \bar{T}^r \\ \underline{P} \leq P_k &\leq \bar{P} \end{aligned}$$

IV.2.10. MPC Operation

The optimization problem is solved at each control step using a receding horizon strategy. Only the first control action $T_0^{sp}, P_0^{PV,used}, P_0^{PV,curt}, P_0^\downarrow$ are actuated by the building management system. At the next control step, the state is updated with new measurements, and the optimization is solved again using updated forecasts.

IV.3. Pilot: EWH Cold Rooms

The pilot features four walk-in fridges and one walk-in freezer. Each of the four fridges contains a specific product type. There is one refrigeration cycle cooling the fridges, which is powered by two compressors: an on/off compressor and a modulated compressor. The refrigeration cycle of the freezer is powered by one on/off compressor. The flexibility of the system is enabled by computing dynamic setpoints for the 5 cold rooms decided by the electricity market, while keeping the temperatures strictly inside the food-safe ranges.

Although the fridges and freezer operate on independent cycles, they are modelled together for two primary reasons: Scalability: Integrating them into a single model ensures that any future hardware or operational changes can be adapted more efficiently. Control Logic: Since the flexibility manager reads and actuates all assets simultaneously, it is more cohesive to bind them within a unified framework.

Figure 10. Simple diagram of the cold rooms and the related compressor setup. The dashed line indicates that the on/off compressor can be bypassed. The diagram does not reflect all parts of the refrigeration cycles.

IV.3.1. Sets and Indices

Table 12. Sets and indices in EWH cold rooms

Symbol	Description
\mathcal{R}	Set of cold rooms
$r \in \mathcal{R}$	Cold room index
$k = 0, \dots, H_u - 1$	Control step
H_u	Number of time steps in the MPC horizon
Δt	Time step
$T = \Delta t \cdot H_u$	Control horizon time

IV.3.2. State Variables

Table 13. State variables in EWH cold rooms

Symbol	Description
T_k^r	Temperature of cold room r at control step k
T_k	Stacked vector of cold room temperatures

IV.3.3. Control Variables

Table 14. Control variables in EWH cold rooms

Symbol	Description
$T_k^{r,sp}$	Temperature setpoint for cold room r
T_k^{sp}	Stacked vector of temperature setpoints

Symbol	Description
p_k^1	Electrical power consumption of the modulated fridge compressor at time k
δ_k^{fridge}	Binary variable indicating if the fridge on/off compressor is active at time k
$\delta_k^{freezer}$	Binary variable indicating if the freezer on/off compressor is active at time k
u_k^r	Allocated electrical power for cooling of cold room $\forall r \in \mathcal{R} \setminus \{5\}$ at time k
$u_k^{r,req}$	Requested electrical power for cooling of cold room $\forall r \in \mathcal{R} \setminus \{5\}$ at time k
P_k^\uparrow	Power sold to the grid
P_k^\downarrow	Power bought from the grid
$P_k^{PV,used}$	PV power used for self-consumption
$P_k^{PV,curt}$	PV power curtailed

IV.3.4. Exogenous State - Origin: Forecasting Service

Table 15. Exogenous state for forecasting service in EWH cold rooms

Symbol	Description
T_k^a	Ambient temperature
$Q_k^{r,door}$	Energy added to cold room r at time k if the door is open
Q_k^{door}	Stacked door openings
P_k^{PV}	PV production forecast
P_k^{rest}	Power consumed by non-controlled assets (rest of hotel)

We define the stacked disturbances $d_k = [T_k^{soil}, Q_k^{r\uparrow}]^\top$.

IV.3.5. Exogenous State - Origin: Trading Manager

Table 16. Exogenous state for the trading manager in EWH cold rooms

Symbol	Description
π_k^\downarrow	Electricity purchase price (ToU)
π_k^\uparrow	Electricity sell price (ToU)

IV.3.6. Algebraic

Table 17. Algebraic symbols in EWH cold rooms

Symbol	Description
$p_k^2 = \delta_k^{fridge} p_{max}^2$	Electrical power consumption of compressor (fridge on/off)
$p_k^3 = \delta_k^{freezer} p_{max}^3$	Electrical power consumption of compressor (freezer on/off)
$P_k = \sum_i p_k^i$	Total power used by the three compressors
$U_k^{req} = \sum_{r \in \mathcal{R} \setminus \{5\}} u_k^{r,req}$	Total requested electrical power for the cooling of the four fridges

IV.3.7. Parameters (Metadata)

Table 18. Parameters in EWH cold rooms

Symbol	Description
\bar{B}	Grid purchase limit
\bar{S}	Grid selling limit
\underline{T}^r	Cold room r temperature lower bound
\bar{T}^r	Cold room r temperature upper bound
\underline{p}	Power consumption lower limit
\bar{p}	Power consumption upper limit
K^{gain}	The electrical power [kW] needed per °C of temperature deviation to drive the cold room from its current temperature toward the setpoint.
M^{fridge}	Large constant used to activate or deactivate the big-M constraint of the fridges
$M^{freezer}$	Large constant used to activate or deactivate the big-M constraint of the freezer

IV.3.8. Digital Twin

The evolution of the cold room state and resulting power consumption are governed by the Digital Twin constraints. The dynamics of the cold rooms are derived from the first law of thermodynamics applied to a lumped thermal mass. This results in the energy balance of a single room.

$$mc_v \frac{dT(t)}{dt} = Q^{ambient}(t) + Q^{door}(t) - Q^{cool}(t)$$

where m [kg] is the effective thermal mass of the room, and c_v [$\frac{J}{kg \cdot K}$] is the specific heat capacity of the thermal mass. The first term approximates the heat transfer with the surrounding through walls, ceiling, and floor (the envelope of the room), given as

$$Q^{ambient}(t) = UA(T^a(t) - T(t))$$

where U [$\frac{W}{m^2 \cdot K}$] is the overall transfer coefficient of the rooms and A [m^2] is the effective surface area of the room envelope.

The second term is the energy added to the room while the door is open. This will be a disturbance and estimated empirically.

The third term is the energy removed by the refrigeration cycle. The energy removed is calculated using a compressor coefficient of performance (COP [–]) as

$$Q^{cool} = COP \cdot P(t)$$

where $P(t)$ [kW] is the power consumed by a compressor.

State space form

The proposed model for all five cold rooms can be written in continuous time on state space form as

$$\dot{x}(t) = Ax(t) + Bu(t) + Ed(t)$$

Where:

$$x(t) = [T^1(t) \quad T^2(t) \quad T^3(t) \quad T^4(t) \quad T^5(t)]^T$$

$$u(t) = [u^1(t) \quad u^2(t) \quad u^3(t) \quad u^4(t) \quad u^5(t)]^T$$

$$d(t) = [T^a(t) \quad Q^{1,door}(t) \quad Q^{2,door}(t) \quad Q^{3,door}(t) \quad Q^{4,door}(t) \quad Q^{5,door}(t)]^T$$

and the matrices are defined as:

$$A = \text{diag} \left(-\frac{U^1 A^1}{m^1 c_v^1}, \dots, -\frac{U^r A^r}{m^r c_v^r} \right)$$

$$B = \text{diag} \left(-\frac{COP^1}{m^1 c_v^1}, \dots, -\frac{COP^r}{m^r c_v^r} \right)$$

$$E = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{U^1 A^1}{m^1 c_v^1} & 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \frac{U^2 A^2}{m^2 c_v^2} & 0 & \frac{1}{m^2 c_v^2} & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{U^r A^r}{m^r c_v^r} & 0 & \dots & 0 & \frac{1}{m^r c_v^r} \end{bmatrix}$$

Discrete time state space model

To use the digital twin in the flexibility optimization it should be discretized. Applying a zero-order hold for the control and disturbance variables, the system can be discretized with a sampling time Δt giving

$$x_{k+1} = A_d x_k + B_d u_k + E_d d_k$$

Where:

$$A_d = e^{A T_s}$$

$$B_d = \int_0^{T_s} e^{A \tau} B d\tau$$

$$E_d = \int_0^{T_s} e^{A \tau} E d\tau$$

The easy calculation of these is done as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} A_d & B_d & E_d \\ 0 & I & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & I \end{bmatrix} = \exp \left(\begin{bmatrix} A & B & E \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} T_s \right)$$

Replication of the compressor controller

As we will only be able to control the setpoints of the cold rooms, a model of the compressor logic needs to be developed for the flexibility optimization. The true physical system driving the compressor power usage is complex and include valve openings and pressures in the refrigeration cycle. To get a suitable model for the optimization we abstract these low-level dynamics by assuming a hierarchical control structure of the compressors driven by the differences in the room temperatures and setpoints.

The on/off compressor of the freezer is switched on and off given a hysteresis band defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Compressor ON} & \quad \text{if } T_k^5 \geq T_k^{5,sp} + d \\ \text{Compressor OFF} & \quad \text{if } T_k^5 \leq T_k^{5,sp} - d \end{aligned}$$

where d [$^{\circ}\text{C}$] is the bandwidth. This can be written as constraints using a big-M notation as

$$\begin{aligned} T_k - (T_{set,k} + d) & \leq M^{freezer} \delta_k^{freezer} \\ (T_{set,k} - d) - T_k & \leq M^{freezer} (1 - \delta_k^{freezer}) \end{aligned}$$

Giving:

$$u_k^5 = \delta_k^{freezer} P_{max}^3$$

The logic for the fridge system is more advanced, as the two compressors in that refrigeration cycle supply cooling for all four fridges. This is handled by calculating the requested power needed for cooling by each of the four fridges and then letting the optimizer delegate the available power for cooling. The requested power is not a variable related to the true system. It is an abstraction that allows the model to handle the distribution of cooling in the fridges without having the knowledge of the expansion valves in the true refrigeration cycle.

The requested electrical power for cooling each of the fridges is given as

$$u_k^{r,req} \geq K^{gain} (T_k^r - T_k^{r,sp})$$

where K^{gain} is a parameter translating the desired temperature change to an electrical power request for the compressors.

The primary modulated compressor ramps up first to meet demand. If the load exceeds its limit, the second on/off compressor kicks in to provide additional power. To model this behavior the primary modulated compressor is a control variable p_k^1 with the constraints

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &\leq p_k^1 \leq P_{max}^1 \\ p_k^1 &\leq U_k^{req} \end{aligned}$$

The logic for activating the on/off compressor for the fridges the following big-M constraint is used

$$\begin{aligned} U_k^{req} - P_{max}^1 &\leq M^{fridge} \delta_k^{fridge} \\ p_k^2 &= \delta_k^{fridge} P_{max}^2 \end{aligned}$$

The allocation to each of the four rooms is then constrained by

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{r \in \mathcal{R} \setminus \{5\}} u_k^r &= p_k^1 + p_k^2 \\ 0 &\leq u_k^r \leq u_k^{r,req}, \quad \forall r \in \mathcal{R} \setminus \{5\} \end{aligned}$$

Simulation code for the cold-room thermal dynamics and compressor-control logic is available in the BlueBird GitHub repository at the path: flexibility-manager/dt/EWH_coldrooms.

IV.3.9. Model Predictive Control

The receding horizon optimization problem reads as:

$$\begin{aligned} &\underset{\substack{T^{sp}, u^r, u^{r,req}, \delta^{freezer}, \delta^{fridge} \\ p^{PV,used}, p^{PV,curt} \\ p^\uparrow, p^\downarrow}}{\text{minimize}} && \sum_{k=0}^{H_u-1} (P_k^\downarrow \pi_k^\downarrow - P_k^\uparrow \pi_k^\uparrow) \Delta t \end{aligned}$$

Subject to ($\forall k = 0, \dots, H_u - 1$):

- Power Balance Constraints:

$$\begin{aligned} P_k^{PV,used} + P_k^\uparrow + P_k^{PV,curt} &= P_k^{PV} \\ P_k^\downarrow + P_k^{PV,used} &= P_k + P_k^{rest} \end{aligned}$$

- Electrical Constraints:

$$\begin{aligned}
0 &\leq P_k^{PV,used} \leq P_k^{PV} \\
0 &\leq P_k^{PV,curt} \leq P_k^{PV} \\
0 &\leq P_k^\uparrow \leq \bar{S} \\
0 &\leq P_k^\downarrow \leq \bar{B} \\
P_k^\uparrow \cdot P_k^\downarrow &= 0
\end{aligned}$$

- State space Constraints:

$$\begin{aligned}
x_{k+1} &= A_d x_k + B_d u_k + E_d d_k \\
x_0 &= x^{inti}
\end{aligned}$$

- Compressor logic Constraints :

$$\begin{aligned}
u_k^{r,req} &\geq Kgain(T_k^r - T_k^{r,sp}) \\
T_k - (T_{set,k} + d) &\leq M^{freezer} \delta_k^{freezer} \\
(T_{set,k} - d) - T_k &\leq M^{freezer} (1 - \delta_k^{freezer}) \\
U_k^{req} - \bar{p}^1 &\leq M^{fridge} \delta_k^{fridge} \\
\delta^{freezer} &\in \{0,1\} \\
\delta^{fridge} &\in \{0,1\}
\end{aligned}$$

- Algebraic:

$$\begin{aligned}
u_k^5 &= p_k^3 = \delta_k^{freezer} \bar{p}^3 \\
p_k^2 &= \delta_k^{fridge} \bar{p}^2 \\
\sum_{r \in \mathcal{R} \setminus \{5\}} u_k^r &= p_k^1 + p_k^2 \\
P_k &= p_k^1 + p_k^2 + p_k^3
\end{aligned}$$

- Bounds:

$$\begin{aligned}
p_k^1 &\leq U_k^{req} \\
\underline{p}^1 &\leq p_k^1 \leq \bar{p}^1 \\
0 &\leq u_k^r \leq u_k^{r,req}, \quad \forall r \in \mathcal{R} \setminus \{5\}
\end{aligned}$$

- Comfort Constraints:

$$\underline{T}^r \leq x_k^r \leq \bar{T}^r$$

IV.3.10. MPC Operation

The optimization problem is solved at each control step using a receding horizon strategy. Only the first control actions, T_0^{sp} , $P_0^{PV,used}$, $P_0^{PV,curt}$, P_0^\uparrow , P_0^\downarrow , are actuated by the management system. At the next control step, the state is updated with new measurements, and the optimization is solved again using updated forecasts.

IV.4. Pilot: Karno District Heating System

The District Heating features a complex architecture, including 2 distinct heat pumps, a 2,5 m2 tank storage and PID logic for heat delivery. The modelling and building of a digital twin are particularly challenging and pure time series analysis as considered in other pilots will not describe the system with sufficient accuracy and confidence for long term (24 - 72 hours) predictions.

A schematic view of the system is described in Figure 11.

Figure 11. Karno district heating schematic representation.

IV.4.1. Sets and Indices

Table 19. Sets and indices in Karno district heating system

Symbol	Description
$k = 0, \dots, H_u - 1$	Control step index
H_u	MPC horizon length
Δt	Time step

IV.4.2. State Variables

Table 20. State variables in Karno district heating system

Symbol	Description	Insight
T_k	Mean Tank Temperature	E (Estimated)
T_{bot}	Tank bottom temperature	M (Measured)
T_{top}	Tank top temperature	M
$T_{out,air}$	Aero Heat pump forward temperature	M
$T_{out,geo}$	Geo Heat pump forward temperature	M
$T_{dist,in}$	District injection temperature	M

Symbol	Description	Insight
$T_{dist,ret}$	District return temperature	M
$\dot{m}_{HP,air}$	Aero Heat Pump mass flow	E
$\dot{m}_{HP,geo}$	Geo Heat Pump mass flow	E

IV.4.3. Control Variables

Table 21. Control variables in Karno district heating system

Symbol	Description
$T_{dist,in}^{ref}$	District input temperature setpoint
$u_{HP,air}$	Aero Heat Pump electrical power
$u_{HP,geo}$	Geo Heat Pump electrical power
$z_{HP,air}$	Aero HP ON/OFF binary
$z_{HP,geo}$	Geo HP ON/OFF binary

IV.4.4. Exogenous States (Disturbances) - origin: Forecasting

Table 22. Exogenous states for forecasting in Karno district heating system

Symbol	Description
T_{air}	Ambient air temperature
T_{ground}	Ground temperature (for Geo HP)
\dot{Q}_{dist}	District heat demand

IV.4.5. Exogenous States (Disturbances) - origin: Trading Manager

Table 23. Exogenous states for the trading manager in Karno district heating system

Symbol	Description
π_k^\downarrow	Electricity purchase price (ToU)

IV.4.6. Algebraic

Table 24. Algebraic symbols in Karno district heating system

Symbol	Description	Formula
$\dot{Q}_{in,air}$	Thermal power from Aero HP	$\dot{m}_{HP,air} c_p T_{out,air}$
$\dot{Q}_{in,geo}$	Thermal power from Geo HP	$\dot{m}_{HP,geo} c_p T_{out,geo}$
$\dot{Q}_{in,tot}$	Total thermal power to tank	$\dot{Q}_{in,air} + \dot{Q}_{in,geo}$
\dot{Q}_{ret}	Thermal power returned to the tank	$\dot{m}_{d2t} c_p T_{dist,ret}$
\dot{m}_{t2d}	Tank to district mass flow	$x_{PID} \cdot \dot{m}_{dist}$
\dot{m}_{d2t}	District to tank mass flow	$x_{PID} \cdot \dot{m}_{dist}$
x_{PID}	PID selection fraction	$(T_{dist,in} - T_{dist,ret}) / (T_{top} - T_{dist,ret})$

IV.4.7. Parameters (Metadata)

Table 25. Parameters symbols in Karno district heating system

Symbol	Description
C	Tank thermal capacity
UA	Tank global heat loss coefficient
$C_{p,HP}$	Heat pump internal thermal capacity
c_p	Specific heat capacity of the fluid
$\theta_{i,air}$	COP coefficients for Aero HP
$\theta_{i,geo}$	COP coefficients for Geo HP
σ_{HP}	Volatility of the temperature process (HP)
σ_{tank}	Volatility of the temperature process (tank)
σ_m	Volatility of the mass flow process
dW_t	Wiener process increment
\bar{P}_{HP}	Maximum heat pump electrical power
\underline{T}_{tank}	Tank temperature lower bound
\bar{T}_{tank}	Tank temperature upper bound
\underline{T}_{dist}	District minimal supply temperature
\bar{T}_{dist}	District maximal supply temperature

IV.4.8. Digital Twin

1. Thermal Storage Tank

The tank is modelled using a single state T representing the average temperature:

$$T = \frac{1}{2}(T_{top} + T_{bot})$$

$$C \frac{dT}{dt} = \dot{Q}_{in,tot} - \dot{Q}_{ret} - \dot{Q}_{dist} - UA(T - T_{air}) + \sigma_{tank} + dW_t$$

2. Heat Pump 1: Aero (Air-Source)

$$C_{p,HP} \frac{dT_{out,air}}{dt} = COP_{air}(T_{out,air}, T_{air}) u_{HP,air} + \dot{m}_{HP,air} c_p (T_{in} - T_{out,air}) + \sigma_{HP} dW_t$$

$$COP_{air} = \theta_{0,air} + \theta_{1,air} T_{air} - \theta_{2,air} T_{out,air}$$

$$d\dot{m}_{HP,air} = 0 + \sigma_m dW_t$$

3. Heat Pump 2: Geo (Geothermal)

$$C_{p,HP} \frac{dT_{out,geo}}{dt} = COP_{geo}(T_{out,geo}, T_{ground}) u_{HP,geo} + \dot{m}_{HP,geo} c_p (T_{in} - T_{out,geo}) + \sigma_{HP} dW_t$$

$$COP_{geo} = \theta_{0,geo} + \theta_{1,geo} T_{ground} - \theta_{2,geo} T_{out,geo}$$

$$d\dot{m}_{HP,geo} = 0 + \sigma_m dW_t$$

A similar approach to EWH fridge enables using measurements to estimate the stochastic differential equations parameters. After the parameters are estimated the system is discretized in a difference equation.

$$x_{k+1} = f(x_k, u_k, d_k)$$

where for simplicity, the state, the control inputs and the disturbances have been stacked in a single vector.

IV.4.9. Model Predictive Control

The receding horizon optimization problem reads as:

$$\underset{\substack{u, x, z \\ T_{dist,in}^{ref}}}{\text{minimize}} \sum_{k=0}^{H_u-1} (u_{HP,air,k} + u_{HP,geo,k}) \cdot \pi_k^{\downarrow} \cdot \Delta t$$

Subject to ($\forall k = 0, \dots, H_u - 1$):

System Dynamics:

$$x_{k+1} = f(x_k, u_k, d_k)$$

Constraints:

- Storage Comfort:

$$\underline{T}_{tank} \leq T_k \leq \bar{T}_{tank}$$

- Power Limits:

$$0 \leq u_{HP,air,k} \leq \bar{P}_{HP,air}$$

$$0 \leq u_{HP,geo,k} \leq \bar{P}_{HP,geo}$$

- Supply Requirements:

$$\underline{T}_{dist} \leq T_{dist} \leq \bar{T}_{dist,in}$$

- Algebraic Relations: Described in the table above.

IV.4.10. MPC Operation

The optimization is solved at each control step. Only the first control action is actuated. At the next step, the state is updated with new measurements, and the optimization is solved again using updated forecasts. The measurements all come with a granularity of 5 minutes. Different MPC horizons will be tried (between 24 and 72 hours) and different time steps (5 min, 15 min, 1 h).

IV.5. Pilot: Enlion, Water Work

This pilot considers a drinking water pumping station supplying a water tower. The system includes four pumps feeding the reservoir. Three pumps are controllable by the flexibility manager, while the fourth pump is kept as an operational reserve for safety and redundancy. The water tower acts as a storage buffer between pumping and consumer demand. By adjusting pump flows while maintaining tank level constraints, the system can provide electrical demand response services to the grid while ensuring reliable water supply.

The site is equipped with photovoltaic (PV) generation. In the present formulation, PV production is considered under a self-consumption only scheme, meaning that PV electricity can be used to supply the pumps but cannot be exported to the grid. Any excess PV production is curtailed.

IV.5.1. Sets and Indices

Table 26. Sets and indices in Enlion Water Work

Symbol	Description
\mathcal{P}	Set of controllable pumps
$i \in \mathcal{P}$	Pump index
$k = 0, \dots, H_u - 1$	Control step
H_u	MPC horizon length
Δt	Time step

IV.5.2. State Variable

Table 27. State variables in Enlion Water Work

Symbol	Description
V_k	Water volume in the reservoir
p_k	Reservoir suction pressure

IV.5.3. Control Variables

Table 28. Control variables in Enlion Water Work

Symbol	Description
$P_{i,k}$	Electrical consumption of pump i
$P_k^{PV,used}$	PV power used for self-consumption
$P_k^{PV,curt}$	PV power curtailed

IV.5.4. Exogenous state (Disturbances) - origin: Forecasting Service

Table 29. Exogenous states for forecasting in Enlion Water Work

Symbol	Description
D_k	Water demand forecast
P_k^{PV}	PV production forecast

IV.5.5. Exogenous state (Disturbances) - origin: Trading Manager

Table 30. Exogenous states for the trading manager in Enlion Water Work

Symbol	Description
R_k^\uparrow	Upward reserve commitment (power reduction capability)
R_k^\downarrow	Downward reserve commitment (power increase capability)

IV.5.6. Algebraic

Table 31. Algebraic symbols in Enlion Water Work

Symbol	Description
$F_{i,k}$	Flow produced by pump i
P_k	Total electrical consumption of pumps

The plant electrical consumption and hydraulic flow are related through nonlinear pump characteristics

$$F_{i,k} = g_i(P_{i,k}, p_k)$$

The total electrical consumption of the pumping station is

$$P_k = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{P}} P_{i,k}$$

IV.5.7. Parameters (metadata)

Table 32. Parameters symbols in Enlion Water Work

Symbol	Description
\underline{V}	Minimum tank volume
\bar{V}	Maximum tank volume
V^{target}	Target terminal tank level
\underline{P}	Minimum plant electrical power
\bar{P}	Maximum plant electrical power
F_i^{avg}	Nominal operating flow of pump i
w	Objective weighting parameter

IV.5.8. Digital Twin

The tank dynamics follow a simple mass balance:

$$V_{k+1} = V_k + \left(\sum_{i \in \mathcal{P}} F_{i,k} - D_k \right) \Delta t$$

The electrical consumption and hydraulic production of each pump are related through nonlinear pump characteristics

$$F_{i,k} = g_i(P_{i,k}, p_k)$$

Both the state evolution and power relations enter as constraints in the Model Predictive Control optimization scheme.

The Digital Twin follows the Digital Twin Framework where Locations are modeled as Digital Areas and (virtual) devices as Digital Device.

The spatial structure of the waterworks facility is modeled by the three hierarchically structured Digital Areas shown in Figure 12: Waterworks Facility, Pumping Station, and Retention Tank Building.

Figure 12. System Model of the Waterworks digital twin

Waterworks Facility

This area represents the entire waterworks facility, encompassing all on-site buildings. It serves as the area hierarchy's root and contains both the Pumping Station and Retention Tank Building as child areas. No Digital Devices or Acceptance Constraints are directly attached to this area.

Pumping Station

This area represents the four pumps that are responsible for extracting groundwater and transferring it to the retention tank. It has no child areas. Four structurally identical Digital Devices are associated with this area, each representing one physical pump. Each pump device has two non-controllable properties—Water Flow and Power Consumption—and one controllable property: Power Setpoint. Water Flow indicates the volumetric flow rate in $\text{m}^3 \text{h}^{-1}$, Power Setpoint specifies the target power level in the interval $[0, 1]$, and Power Consumption reflects the electrical demand for this target power level in watts. The physical constraints are defined as follows: Water Flow is constrained to values between zero and the minimum of the upper-bound pump flow rate and pipe throughput; Power Consumption must be non-negative; and Power Setpoint is constrained to the interval $[0, 1]$. The get values of each property reference a unique database identifier for retrieving measurements. The Power Setpoint includes the control interface endpoint for actuating the pump. Water Flow and Power Consumption are classified as dependent variables, as their values are determined by the Power Setpoint, which is the sole independent variable. No Acceptance Constraints are attached to this area.

Retention Tank Building

This area represents the building containing the retention tank. It is positioned at a higher elevation to enable gravity-fed water distribution to consumers. It has no child areas. The area contains a single Digital Device named Retention Tank with two non-controllable properties: Tank Level and Outflow. Tank Level represents the current water volume in m^3 , while Outflow indicates the discharge rate in $\text{m}^3 \text{h}^{-1}$. The Tank Level is physically bounded empty and full capacity, and the Outflow is constrained to the range between zero and the maximum pipe throughput. The get value represents a unique identifier in a database for the Tank Level and Outflow respectively. Tank Level is marked as a dependent variable, as it is influenced by other system properties such as inflow and outflow, whereas Outflow is classified as independent within our model scope. An Acceptance Constraint is attached to this area: The Tank Level must never fall below a certain threshold to ensure sufficient water reserves for emergency situations that require rapid supply to consumers.

When training the digital twin on synthetically generated data, the trained dynamics are following the actual data closely. Figure 13, Figure 14, and Figure 15 show the predicted values vs the real observed values of the tank level, pumping power and pump flow. The predictions are started with an initial state after which only predicted values are used to predict next steps, showing the real performance of the model rather than only showing the prediction capabilities of one step. The predictions are done for a time horizon of three days ahead with one hour time steps.

Figure 13. Three days ahead prediction of total pump power in kW

Figure 14. Three days ahead prediction of tank level power in kW

Figure 15. Three days ahead prediction of water flow of pump-1 in kW

IV.5.9. Predictive Control

The problem consists of having the reserve to provide the committed reserve (capacity) on the day-ahead market while moving away from a historical baseline only smoothly. The trade-off is made by the weighting parameter w .

The receding horizon optimization problem reads as:

$$\underset{P, V, P^{PV,used}, P^{PV,curt}}{\text{minimize}} \sum_{k=0}^{H_u-1} \left[(1-w) \sum_{i \in \mathcal{P}} (F_{i,k} - F_i^{avg})^2 + w \left((\bar{P} - P_k - R_k^\downarrow)^2 + (P_k - \underline{P} - R_k^\uparrow)^2 \right) \right]$$

subject to ($\forall k = 0, \dots, H_u - 1$):

- Tank dynamics:

$$V_{k+1} = V_k + \left(\sum_{i \in \mathcal{P}} F_{i,k} - D_k \right) \Delta t$$

- Tank constraints:

$$\underline{V} \leq V_k \leq \bar{V}$$

- Electrical power constraints:

$$\underline{P} \leq P_k \leq \bar{P}$$

- PV self-consumption constraints:

$$0 \leq P_k^{PV,used} \leq P_k^{PV}$$

$$0 \leq P_k^{PV,used} \leq P_k$$

$$P_k^{PV,used} + P_k^{PV,curt} = P_k^{PV}$$

- Terminal constraint:

$$V_{H_u} \geq V^{target}$$

IV.5.10. MPC Operation

The optimization problem is solved at each control step using a receding horizon strategy.

Only the first control action $P_{i,0}$ is applied to the pumping station. At the next control step, the tank level is updated with new measurements, and the optimization is solved again using updated demand forecasts, PV forecasts, and reserve commitments.

IV.6. Pilot: EWH EV-Charging

This pilot considers an electric vehicle (EV) charging station (CS) situated in Hotel Prinz Luitpold Bad. The hotel owns 4 stations for the guests, where they can plug and charge the car. Right now, the stations are automatically charging when plugged, and an improvement can be done by smartly charging the EVs deciding to charge or not charge in different times based on current energy price.

IV.6.1. EV-Charger description

Every CS has a nominative power of 11 kW, constantly providing it to the plugged EV. The CS can then provide full power (11 kW) or nothing (0 kW), without considering the EV power limitation. EV stations are not allowed to charge at full power together, since there is an overall power capacity constraint of 30 kW.

The main objective is to control the EV station smartly, by using Reinforcement Learning (RL), as shown later. The goal is to charge vehicles with a good amount of energy, and on the same time charging when prices are low. We first formalize the problem as a Markov Decision Problem (see next section), and then we use RL for deciding when to charge at each step.

To take actions with RL, we first define the infrastructure and discretize the time in which we decide the actions. As said before, we consider $S \in \mathbb{N}$ stations, 4 in our case, and each station can serve one EV at time, delivering constant charging power. Time is discretized into fixed intervals of duration Δt , in our case equals to 15 minutes.

The maximum energy that can be delivered to an EV is defined by:

$$E_{\Delta} = P_{kw} \cdot \frac{\Delta}{60}.$$

The system receives a sequence of EV sessions, and for each EV, we know:

1. Arrival time a_i
2. Departure time d_i
3. Required Energy E_i^{req}
4. Assigned station s_i , with $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, S\}$

While connected, the EV accumulates delivered energy:

$$E_i^{del}(t) = \sum_{\tau=a_i}^t E_i(\tau)$$

Remaining energy for the EV will be:

$$E_i^{rem}(t) = E_i^{req} - E_i^{del}(t).$$

At every time interval t , a market electricity price $p_t \in \mathbb{R}$ is known.

At every time interval t , the controller must select an action for each station:

$$a_t = (a_{t,1}, a_{t,2}, \dots, a_{t,S}) \in \{0,1\}^S$$

where $a_{t,s} = 1$ means station S charges its EV, and $a_{t,s} = 0$ means station S idles in that interval.

The energy delivered at station s in interval t is:

$$E_{t,s} = a_{t,s} \cdot \min(E_{\Delta}, E_i^{rem}(t))$$

and the charging cost at station s is:

$$C_{t,s} = p_t \cdot E_{t,s}.$$

IV.6.2. MDP Formulation

The charging scheduling problem is modelled as a finite-horizon Markov Decision Process (MDP), which is the most common solution for describing a decision-making problem while interacting with an environment.

IV.6.2.a. State space

The state at time t denoted s_t , encodes:

1. Price information, i.e. the price at next step p_{t+1} and a window of historical prices $(p_t, p_{t-1}, \dots, p_{t-W+1})$.

2. Time-of-day encoding, by using sine and cosine to represent daily periodicity: $\sin\left(2\pi \frac{time(t)}{24h}\right)$, $\cos\left(2\pi \frac{time(t)}{24h}\right)$
3. EV information per station: for each stations $= 1, \dots, S$, EV presence $x_{t,s}^{pres} \in \{0,1\}$, remaining energy $x_{t,s}^{rem} = E_{i_s}^{rem}(t)$, time until departure $x_{t,s}^{left} = d_{i_s} - t$, and urgency metric $x_{t,s}^{urg} = \frac{x_{t,s}^{rem}}{P_{kw} \cdot x_{t,s}^{left}}$ are given.

All that information is composing our state s_t at time t .

IV.6.2.b. Action space

Binary vector of length S : $a_t = (a_{t,1}, \dots, a_{t,S})$ with $a_{t,s} \in \{0,1\}$. Invalid actions like charging empty stations are effectively neutral, and they will not affect the output.

IV.6.2.c. Transition dynamics

Transition dynamics define the change of the systemic change of the model over time. In our work, the environment is deterministic given the datasets. The energy delivery is:

$$E_{t,s} = a_{t,s} \cdot \min(E_{\Delta}, E_{i_s}^{rem}(t)).$$

All update state variables, such as remaining energy, departure checks, ... are then updated and the time advances from t to $t + \Delta t$. If an EV departs, all the state variables are set to zero for our agent.

IV.6.2.d. Reward Function

The reward function is used for training the agent at choosing the right, or best, action for each time step. In this case, the cumulative reward over time is defined as:

$$R_t = - \sum_{s=1}^S C_{t,s} - \sum_{s=1}^S \Pi_{t,s}$$

Here, the charging cost is defined by $C_{t,s} = p_t \cdot E_{t,s}$, and the penalty is composed by two parts:

- penalty for undercharging at departure: if the EV departs with remaining energy $E_{rem} > \delta$, penalty is $\Pi_{t,s}^{dep} = fix + var \cdot E_{rem}$. Here, fix is a fixed value for always give a minimum amount of penalty, while var is for penalizing based on the remaining amount of kWh.
- Penalty applied if it is impossible to fully charge the car. If the amount of required energy is lower than the possible deliverable energy at time t , we apply $\Pi_{t,s}^{impossible} = \frac{fix}{2}$

The final reward will be the negative of the total cost for buying energy, plus the penalty (negative) for undercharging the vehicle. This will guarantee a good amount of charging, and on the same time charging at lower costs.

IV.6.3. Reinforcement Learning for EV Charging Scheduling

For solving the previously defined MDP problem, Reinforcement Learning (RL) will be used. RL is a type of machine learning (ML) where a defined agent makes decisions by interacting with an environment, in our case, the EV charging station environment. The agent learns through trial-and-error, receiving rewards for good actions and penalties for bad ones to maximize its long-term cumulative reward defined before.

In this EV-charging problem, the controller must make sequential decisions over time, when to charge each EV and when to wait, to minimize energy cost while respecting each vehicle's departure deadline and required energy.

In RL terms, the agent must learn a policy defined as $\pi(a|s)$ that map each observed system state, price trends, EV requirements, time to departure, to an action vector specifying which stations should charge during the current interval. The goal is to maximize expected discounted return, where rewards encode economic performance and constraint satisfaction.

The goal is to maximize the expected discounted return, defined as:

$$J(\pi) = E_{\pi} \left[\sum_{t=0}^T \gamma^t R_t \right]$$

where R_t is the immediate reward at time t (in our case, the negative charging cost minus penalties), $\gamma \in [0,1]$ is called discount factor, which tells as how far we are looking in the future (the biggest, the more we look at future actions), and T is the final time step.

The goal is to train our agent to obtain the highest reward as possible, and then to find an optimal policy $\pi^*(s) = \arg \max_a Q(s, a)$, with $Q(s, a)$ being the Bellman optimality equation, i.e., a function that tells that the optimal value of a state equals its maximum possible immediate reward plus the discounted value of the next state under a given policy: $Q^*(s, a) = R(s, a) + \gamma \sum_{s'} P(s'|s, a) \max_{a'} Q^*(s', a')$, where s, a are the current state and action and s', a' are the future state and action.

IV.6.3.a. Deep Q-Learning (DQN)

In this EV-charging control problem, Deep Q-Learning (DQN) is used. The DQN agent learns an approximation of the optimal action-value function $Q^*(s, a)$ which, as said before, represents the long-term benefit of applying a charging pattern in a defined state.

DQN uses a neural network $Q_{\theta}(s, a)$ to estimate the function and approximate it, and updates its parameters by minimizing the temporal-difference (TD) loss:

$$L(\theta) = \left(R_t + \gamma \max_{a'} Q_{\theta^-}(s_{t+1}, a') - Q_{\theta}(s_t, a_t) \right)^2$$

Here, Q_{θ} is the online network that learn every step, while Q_{θ^-} is the target network, that is updated slowly to guarantee more stability, and R_t reflects the energy cost, plus EV penalty in our environment.

By iteratively applying the TD update during simulated interaction, the network learns a cost-optimal charging strategy that balances avoiding expensive periods with ensuring all EVs finish charging before their deadlines.

The trained DQN can be then tested and compared, for showing eventual better results w.r.t. rule-based, always charge solutions.

To conclude, the DQN agent is trained on 70% of the historical EV-charging dataset, iteratively observing the current state and updating its neural-network parameters through temporal-difference learning to minimize long-term charging cost and penalties. During training, the agent repeatedly experiences the effects of its actions on future states and receives rewards that guide the optimization of the Q-function. In the test phase, the remaining 30% of the data is used to evaluate the learned policy: instead of updating its parameters, the agent simply selects at each time step the action vector that maximizes the predicted Q-value, producing an optimal charging schedule based on the patterns learned during training.

IV.7. Second phase buildings status

In some cases, no WP3 modelling work was started due to different reasons. The implementation plans created in summer 2025 (and documented in D2.1) already pointed to some challenges.

AMB: Sports Center building (IEB) and Civic Centre building (CCB)

At AMB, the focus of the first year was put on the Montcada building, where some basic sensing had already been installed at the beginning of the project, so that the DT task was started there. In the CCB, there are delays in the implementation plan due to connectivity issues with the BMS, which, for the moment, are blocking the data-gathering phase. On the IEB, as indicated in the implementation plan, all devices were installed at the beginning of 2026. The digital twin task can start after collecting some historical data.

The digital twin task in the CCB is expected to use an adaptation of the Montcada Building as both are multizone buildings using the flexibility of the HVAC system. Therefore, both buildings' time series modelling and control approach will be similar. Moreover, the IEB, being a sports centre with a heated pool and DHW, will follow a physics-based grey-box modelling approach similar to Karno district heating and EWH cold rooms demo cases.

ENEA Office and ENEA Grid

These pilots are being implemented in parallel, as the procurement process is the same for both buildings. As ENEA is part of the critical infrastructure, procurement was very challenging, and, additionally, the tender process was subject to regulation, which led to a 2/3-month delay in relation to the implementation plan. Meanwhile, installations are ongoing, and it is foreseen that data collection will start mid-April, as in parallel, all the IT infrastructure required for data collection has already been installed and prepared.

WeSmart

WeSmart T&T originally was also understood as a multi-zonal building with opportunities to create a FM optimizing power consumption. However, during UC and data availability discussions it turned out that T&T, although having access to data per apartment (which was set up at the beginning of 2026), has no direct control over devices in the apartments, so that, apart from forecasting, this is a predominantly social pilot. So, modelling focus was more on the other pilots. WeSmart GreenBiz, with PV, EV and battery storage does offer central optimization options, however, data are not yet available.

V. SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE

V.1. Overview

The WP3 software architecture follows a modular and service-oriented design. Each component exposes a minimal API allowing independent development and deployment while ensuring interoperability between modules.

The main components involved in the control workflow are:

- Flexibility Manager
- Digital Twin
- Forecasts Module
- Knowledge Engine

Operational data such as sensor measurements and forecasts are stored in the pilot databases. The Flexibility Manager retrieves these data when executing the optimization routine.

A detailed description of the database infrastructure is provided in Deliverable D6.1.

Market-related signals used in the optimization are provided by the Knowledge Engine, described in Deliverable D5.1.

V.2. APIs

The BlueBird WP3 architecture relies on a set of well-defined APIs allowing the different software modules to exchange information. These interfaces ensure that each component can be developed and deployed independently while maintaining consistent data exchange.

V.2.1. Flexibility Manager

The Flexibility Manager computes optimal actuator setpoints using a Model Predictive Control (MPC) routine.

The high-level interface can be expressed as:

$$u_{\{t:t+T\}} = \text{optimize}(x_t, d_{\{t:t+T\}}, A_t, B_t, G_t)$$

where:

- x_t is the current system state obtained from sensor measurements,
- $d_{\{t:t+T\}}$ represents the forecast disturbances over the prediction horizon,
- A_t , B_t , and G_t are the system dynamics obtained from the Digital Twin.

The optimization returns the control sequence over the horizon. In practice, only the first control action is applied before the next MPC update.

In the implementation, the main API entry point is:

```
optimize(digital_twin_file, sensors_file, forecasts_file; kwargs...)
```

This function loads the required data, builds the optimization problem, and returns the computed control setpoints.

V.2.2. Digital Twin

The Digital Twin provides the system dynamics required by the optimization routine.

The interface allows the Flexibility Manager to obtain a state-space representation of the system at the current operating point:

$$A_t, B_t, E_t = \text{extract_dynamics}(x_t, u_t, t)$$

Although the underlying system may be nonlinear, the Digital Twin exposes a linearized representation suitable for efficient optimization.

The Digital Twin may also provide a prediction interface used for validation and simulation purposes:

$$x_{\{t+1\}} = \text{predict_state}(x_t, u_t, d_t)$$

This function computes the next state of the system based on the current state, control input, and disturbances.

V.2.3. Forecast Module

Forecasts of external disturbances such as weather conditions, building electricity demand, or photovoltaic production are generated by a dedicated forecasting service.

The service periodically writes updated forecasts to the pilot database. These forecasts are then retrieved by the Flexibility Manager when executing the optimization routine.

Conceptually, the forecasting interface can be represented as:

$$d_{\{t:t+T\}} = \text{extract_forecasts}(t)$$

Depending on the pilot infrastructure, forecasting models may be updated periodically or retrained online when sufficient computational resources are available (e.g., GPU-equipped systems).

V.2.4. Knowledge Engine

Market-related signals used by the optimization are provided by the Knowledge Engine (KE).

Knowledge Engine (by TNO) is an open-source semantic interoperability platform designed to enable intelligent data exchange between different systems (e.g., devices, APIs, databases, services) without relying on a central database. It uses semantic technologies and ontologies to define a shared domain language so that disparate systems can understand, link and reason about data across organizational and technical boundaries. A detailed description of the Knowledge Engine is given in D5.1.

To enable communication with the KE service, a dedicated Python client library called KE PYClient (ke-pyclient) was developed. The library allows services to exchange information using predefined graph patterns and configured knowledge interaction (POST, ASK, REACT or ANSWER). It handles semantic communication with the KE server and exposes a simple API for Python-based services and scripts. Each service requires defined semantic graph patterns with configured interaction type and python class models mapping graph bindings (variables) with to class attributes. A detailed description of the client configuration and usage is given in D5.1.

The main interfaces include:

$$\pi_{\{t:t+T\}} = \text{extract_ToU_price}(t)$$

which returns the time-of-use electricity prices over the prediction horizon, and

$$C_{\{t+H:t+H+N\}} = \text{extract_capacity}(u_t, t)$$

which provides market capacity information for future market horizons (e.g., day-ahead markets).

V.3. Software Structure of the Flexibility Manager

The Flexibility Manager is implemented in Julia and organized into two main layers:

1. Core optimization framework
2. Pilot-specific implementations

The core framework contains generic functionality shared across pilots, including input parsing, constraint generation, and solver interaction.

Pilot-specific modules extend this core framework to implement the models and constraints associated with each pilot.

A simplified structure of the codebase is shown below:

This separation allows the generic optimization infrastructure to remain independent from pilot-specific models.

V.4. Pilot Abstraction using Multiple Dispatch

The Flexibility Manager relies on Julia’s multiple dispatch mechanism to handle different pilot implementations within a unified framework.

An abstract type of hierarchy defines different classes of systems:

```

abstract type AbstractBuilding end
abstract type AbstractHeatBuilding <: AbstractBuilding end
abstract type AbstractElecBuilding <: AbstractBuilding end

```

Each pilot is represented as a concrete type:

```

struct Montcada <: AbstractElecBuilding end
struct EWH <: AbstractElecBuilding end
struct Karno <: AbstractHeatBuilding end

```

When the optimization API is called, the pilot identifier is resolved into the corresponding building type. The system then automatically dispatches the appropriate implementation of functions such as:

- `parse_digital_twin`
- `parse_forecasts`

- *build_constraints*
- *mpc_update*

This mechanism allows each pilot to define its own models and constraints while reusing the shared infrastructure of the Flexibility Manager.

V.5. Modular Deployment

The architecture is designed so that the core optimization framework can be distributed as a standalone Julia package (FlexOPTi), while individual pilot implementations can be provided as separate packages.

This modular approach simplifies maintenance and allows deployments to include only the pilots required for a given installation.

The github instance can be found here:

<https://github.com/BlueBird-project/flexibility-manager.git>

V.6. Containerized Deployment

The WP3 software components will be deployed using Docker containers to simplify installation and ensure reproducibility across pilot environments.

Each major component of the architecture can be packaged as an independent container, including:

- Flexibility Manager
- Digital Twin services
- Forecasting services
- Knowledge Engine interfaces

The forecasting module runs independently and periodically updates forecasts in the pilot database. Depending on the available infrastructure, forecasting models may also be retrained online within the containerized environment.

Containerization allows the components to be deployed on heterogeneous infrastructures while maintaining consistent execution environments.

Communication between components is performed through the defined APIs and through access to the pilot databases where operational data (sensors, forecasts, and market signals) are stored.

This approach simplifies integration with the pilot infrastructures and facilitates testing, updates, and scaling of the system.

VI. CONCLUSION

This deliverable has presented the preliminary technical developments of WP3, which form the backbone of BlueBird’s flexibility extraction and optimisation capabilities. A unified framework based on digital twins, forecasting services, and optimisation under uncertainty has been established to enable buildings to participate intelligently in energy and flexibility markets.

The presented results demonstrate the feasibility of combining optimisation-based control, such as robust Model Predictive Control, with data-driven modelling and learning approaches, including Reinforcement Learning. Together, these methods provide a flexible and extensible decision-making layer capable of addressing different levels of model availability, uncertainty, and market interaction.

Toward Deliverable D3.2, the work will be extended in several key directions. First, the WP3 software components will be consolidated to operate seamlessly through containerized deployments and well-defined APIs. Second, digital twin models and control strategies will be fully defined, implemented, and validated for all BlueBird pilot sites. Third, a modular software architecture will be reinforced to allow straightforward integration of new buildings, electricity market mechanisms, and forecasting models. Finally, the modelling and control approaches will be extended or refined where necessary, including the adoption of more advanced or alternative methods, if the preliminary results indicate that improved performance or robustness is required.

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ANNEX I: DIGITAL TWIN DEFINITION FOR MULTI-ZONE BUILDING

Digital Twin definition for Multi zone building - Casa de la Vila

In order to prioritise the use of the generated electricity from the PV plant to climatize the Casa la Vila building, it is necessary to optimise the HVAC system operation. For this purpose, a sequential decision algorithm is used. This operation strategy consists of deciding the operation of the controllable inputs in order to maximise the benefits, defined by a cost function. In this case, the cost functions are defined by minimising the energy cost and maximising the energy capacity.

Therefore, to run this optimisation, it is necessary to model both the internal temperature behaviour and the HVAC system's electrical consumption.

To make these models, data from all the rooms in the building, the overall consumption of the HVAC system and the building's total electricity consumption have been registered.

This use case code is uploaded to: <https://github.com/BlueBird-project/flexibility-manager/tree/main/dt/BlueBird-multizone-modelling/BC2 - Montcada building>

Resources used:

[Data-Driven Virtual Replication of Thermostatically Controlled Domestic Heating Systems](https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2666546822000222)
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2666546822000222>, [Decision-Focused Learning for Neural Network-Constrained Optimization: Application to HVAC Management System](#)

[Onlineforecast: An R Package for Adaptive and Recursive Forecasting](#)

Decision-Making process description

To face this problem, the whole building is split into building zones, each corresponding to one room. A modelling approach has been developed to simulate the internal temperature of each room when the room's HVAC system is powered, depending on whether it is in cooling or heating mode. Later, the estimated internal temperatures are used to estimate the HVAC energy required to condition the spaces. An energy model is constructed for this purpose. Since there are separate readings for total energy and HVAC system energy, the HVAC energy is modelled separately from the non-HVAC energy. For this reason, another model for the non-HVAC energy is constructed and used to estimate this part of the overall consumption. Finally, an optimisation algorithm uses the models' outputs to set the next-step temperature setpoints, thereby reducing energy costs. The pipeline for the decision-making process is shown in the following image:

Figure 1. Pipeline of training, prediction and Dynamics Estimation processes.

As can be seen in the picture, there are three different processes:

- **Digital Twin Training Process:** this process consists of training and generating the Digital Twin (DT) models, which will be used independently later by others to predict or estimate the dynamics at any moment
- **Prediction process:** this process consists of generating the energy prediction with the new data coming from the optimisation process and the different APIs.
- **Dynamics Estimation process:** this process consists on generating the transformed inputs and the matrix coefficients of the dynamics of the model needed by the optimisation process.

Digital Twin Training Process

The Digital Twin Training Process follows three stages:

Stage 1: HVAC model using Machine Learning (ML) approach

Model the temperature of each room depending on the outdoor meteorological variables, the effect of the adjoining rooms, the internal gains and the HVAC system gain.

$$T_r = f(B(SP_r), B(T_r), B(T_o), B(T_{cs}), SP_{cs}, WF)$$

$B(SP_r)$ = regression series setpoint of the room temperature → **controllable input**

$B(T_r)$ = autoregression terms of the room temperature

$B(T_o)$ = regression series of the outdoor temperature

$B(T_c)$ = regression series of the previous adjoining spaces temperature

SP_{cs} = actual setpoint of the adjoining spaces' temperature multiplied by their HVAC status

WF = weather features

Stage 2: Energy model using a Decision Focused Learning (DFL) approach

The estimated temperatures of each room are used to estimate the energy that the HVAC system must provide to go from the previous temperature to the new one for each room. The energy apportionments required for each room are combined to obtain the total energy that the HVAC must apportion. Also, outdoor meteorological variables and the previous values of the energy consumption are considered in the equation to assess its efficiency behaviour.

$$E = f\left(\sum_{r=1}^R ((T_t^{i,r} - T_{t-1}^{i,r}) \times HVAC^{st,r}), WF, N^{hvac}\right)$$

$T^{i,r}$ = internal temperature of room (r)

$HVAC^{st,r}$ = status of the HVAC system of room (r)

WF = weather features

N^{hvac} = number of HVAC systems operating

Stage 3: Calendar-based energy consumption

Since there are separate lectures on total energy consumption and HVAC system energy, the HVAC energy can be subtracted from the total consumption to determine the energy used by other systems, such as lighting and computers. Given that there is no information available on the use of these other systems, a calendar-based model will be utilised to estimate this portion of the building's energy consumption, particularly since it is a tertiary building. The calendar features are complemented by the number of operating HVAC (N^{hvac}) variables, since it's known that they have an impact on this part of the total consumption. Additionally, the outdoor temperature variable is included to capture its impact on occupants' behaviour throughout the year.

$$E = f(CF, n^{hvac}, T^e)$$

CF = calendar features

n^{hvac} = number of HVAC systems operating

T^e = outdoor temperature

Stage 1: Model the temperature for each room (r)

First, for each space (r), the value of the variable that indicates the status of the HVAC system in the room ($\Phi_t^{st,r}$) is evaluated. This variable indicates if the HVAC systems are ON (1) or OFF (0), indicating when the HVAC systems for each space are powered:

$$\Phi_t^{st,r} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if ON} \\ 0 & \text{if OFF} \end{cases}$$

The HVAC model for each room will only be used with the samples where the status of the HVAC system ($\Phi_t^{st,r}$) is 1 (ON).

Also, considering that the rooms are air-conditioned by an HVAC system that can work in either cooling or heating mode, a variable ($H^{m,r}$) is used to differentiate between these two operation modes:

$$H_t^{m,r} = \begin{cases} \geq 3 & \text{if cooling mode} \\ \leq 2 & \text{if heating mode} \end{cases}$$

Depending on the operation mode, two models will be used: one for cooling and one for heating. This is because the relationship between the temperature (output) and the predictors can vary depending on the operating mode.

The model consists of an ARX trained with Recursive Least Squares (RLS).

$$\begin{aligned} \phi(B)T_t^{i,r} &= \gamma_t(B)T_t^{sp,r} + \omega_{elp,t}(B)T_t^{e,lp} \\ &+ \sum_{k=1}^K (\beta_t T_t^{sp,k}) + \sum_{k=1}^K (\omega_{c,k,t}(B)T_t^{c,k} + \\ &\omega_{i,t}(W_t^{s,lp} \times W_t^{d,fs} \times \Psi_t) + \omega_{s,t}(I_t^{sol,lp} \times S_t^{az,fs} \times S_t^{el,fs}) + \epsilon_t \end{aligned}$$

Considering that, depending on the HVAC operation mode, the HVAC will only provide temperature to the room, depending on whether the setpoint ($T^{sp,r}$) is below (cooling) or above (heating) the temperature of the room ($T^{i,r}$), this variable is transformed as:

$$T^{sp,r} = \begin{cases} T^{sp,r} & \text{if } (H^{m,r} > 2) \& (T^{sp,r} - T^{i,r} < C) \\ T^{sp,r} & \text{if } (H^{m,r} < 3) \& (T^{sp,r} - T^{i,r} > C) \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases}$$

Where C is a constant added as a hysteresis. It can be adjusted, for example, using the sensitivity of the temperature sensor:

$$C = \begin{cases} \text{sensitivity} & \text{if cooling mode} \\ \text{-sensitivity} & \text{if heating mode} \end{cases}$$

In the model, all the terms with the backward shift operator (B) are the autoregressive terms, while the others are the linear parameters. Regarding the autoregressive terms, they are defined as:

$$f(B) = 1 + f_1 B^1 \dots + f_n B^n$$

where: n is the number of lags, or order, of the backward shift operator B

The predicted temperature for the time period t is then estimated as:

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{T}_t^{i,r} = & \sum_{l=1}^L \phi_{l,t} T_{t-l}^{i,r} + \sum_{n=0}^N \gamma_{n,t} T_{t-n}^{sp,r} + \sum_{r=0}^R \omega_{elp,r,t} T_{t-r}^{e,lp} + \sum_{k=1}^K \beta_{k,t} T_t^{sp,k} + \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{p=1}^P \omega_{c,k,p,t} T_{t-p}^{c,k} + \\ & \omega_{i,t} (W_t^{s,lp} \times W_t^{d,fs} \times \Psi_t) + \\ & \omega_{s,t} (I_t^{sol,lp} \times S_t^{az,fs} \times S_t^{el,fs}) + \epsilon_t \end{aligned}$$

Where K refers to the number of adjoining rooms, L denotes the number of autoregression temperature lags, N denotes the number of temperature setpoint lags considered, R denotes the number of lags of outdoor temperature considered, and p denotes the number of lags of the adjoining rooms temperature considered. Also, as can be observed in the equation, all the coefficients that relate the input variables with the outputs are time variants; this is due to the fact that the training method used enables having an adaptive model that can adapt its coefficients when new data is available. The training method is described below.

Model's nomenclature:

$\Phi^{st,r}$ = HVAC systems status for the room r

$H_t^{m,r}$ = HVAC systems operation mode indicator for the room r , possible status: 0-Hot_Water, 1-Heating, 2-Heating_Eco, 3-Anti_Freeze, 4-Cooling

$T^{i,r}$ = Indoor temperature of the room r

T^e = Outdoor temperature.

$T^{e,lp}$ = Low-pass filtered outdoor temperature

$T^{sp,r}$ = setpoint temperature of the room r

$T^{sp,k}$ = setpoint temperature of each of the adjoining rooms (c)

$T^{c,k}$ = adjoining space k raw temperature to consider fast changes in indoor temperatures due to changes in the daily minimum and maximum adjoining spaces' temperatures.

$W^{s,lp}$ = Low-pass filtered wind speed

$W^{d,fs}$ = Fourier series of the wind direction

Ψ = temperature difference between indoors of room r and outdoors ($\Psi = T^{i,r} - T^e$)

$I^{sol,lp}$ = Low-pass filtered solar direct normal irradiance

$S^{az,fs}$ = Fourier series of the solar azimuth

$S^{el,fs}$ = Solar elevation

Model inputs:

- Time-lagged (n) indoor temperature of the room ($T_{t-n}^{i,r}$) to characterise the inertia of the building.
- Low-pass filtered regression terms about outdoor temperature ($T^{e,lp}$) to characterise the heat losses through the envelope of the building due to changes in the outdoor temperature.
- Low-pass filtered regression terms about the temperature of the adjoining room k ($T^{e,k,lp}$) to characterise the heat losses or gains through the walls of the building due to changes in the adjoining spaces' temperature.
- Low-pass filtered regression terms about the setpoint temperatures of the HVAC system of the room ($T^{sp,r}$) are used to characterise the increase or decrease in the indoor temperature due to the operation of the HVAC system of the room.
- The setpoint temperatures of the HVAC system of the adjoining rooms ($T^{sp,k}$). Since the temperature of the adjoining spaces for the instant t is not known, their setpoint at this instant are used instead.
- Wind speed ($W^{s,lp}$), interacting with the Fourier series of the wind direction ($W^{d,fs}$) and the temperature difference between indoors and outdoors ($\Psi = T^{i,r} - T^e$) to characterise the heat losses due to air leakage and convection effects through the envelope.
- Solar direct normal irradiance ($I^{sol,lp}$), interacting with the Fourier series of the solar azimuth ($S^{az,fs}$) and of the solar elevation ($S^{el,fs}$) to characterise the solar gains of the room.

$w_t^{f,esc}$ = HVAC system fan speed+1 (to avoid 0 values)

Training function cost:

Since a machine learning model is used, the model's hyperparameters and coefficients must be obtained during training. During this process, a cost function must be chosen to evaluate performance. The cost function chosen for this model is the RMSE between the predicted and measured temperatures.

To track changes in the thermal behaviour of building rooms over time, the model is trained using a Recursive Least Squares (RLS) approach. This training approach is used to create an adaptive model, enabling continuous update of its coefficients as new data arrives. The objective during the training process is to minimise the cost function equation defined by:

$$J(\theta) = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda^{k-i} (y_i - \theta^\top x_i)^2$$

Where θ is the parameter vector to be estimated, y_i is the vector of observations, x_i is the vector of input variables, and λ is the forgetting factor that determines the weight given to the past observations. By adjusting λ , the speed at which the model can adapt to the new data can be adjusted. Since the variation in building space behaviour, and consequently their thermal model behaviour, depends on their usage, the parameter λ can take different values depending on the studied room, and for different buildings, it can take different values depending on the studied room and for different buildings. For this reason, this parameter is included as a hyperparameter in the model, which is tuned during the training process.

In the RLS approach, the coefficients are calculated recursively. This approach consists of a Kalman filter with the model coefficients in the state vector. If only the 0 horizon is used, the coefficients are updated at each time step t by:

$$R_t = \lambda R_{t-1} + x_t x_t^\top$$

$$\theta_t = \theta_{t-1} + R_t^{-1} x_t (y_t - x_t^\top \theta_{t-1})$$

Stage 2: Heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) energy consumption estimation

First, for each space (r), the value of the variable that indicates the status of the HVAC system in the room ($\Phi_t^{st,r}$) is evaluated. This variable indicates if the HVAC systems are ON (1) or OFF (0), indicating when the HVAC systems for each space are powered:

$$\Phi_t^{st,r} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if ON} \\ 0 & \text{if OFF} \end{cases}$$

Since the original variable can have lower granularity than the one used in the model, this variable can take any value between 0 and 1, depending on how many times the HVAC system has operated during the time step used as the acquisition time.

Also, considering that the rooms are air-conditioned by an HVAC system that can work in either cooling or heating mode, a variable is added to differentiate between these two operation modes:

$$H_t^{m,r} = \begin{cases} \geq 3 & \text{if cooling mode} \\ \leq 2 & \text{if heating mode} \end{cases}$$

Since sometimes the HVAC operation mode of a specific room ($H_t^{m,r}$) can be misconfigured, a variable indicating the most frequent value (mode) of all the HVAC operation modes of the building:

$$H_t^m = H_t^{m,r} \text{ with the highest frequency}$$

By using this variable, it is possible to linearise the relation between the energy consumption and the temperature increment required for each room. Also, it must be considered that if the operation mode of a specific room ($H_t^{m,r}$) does not have the same value as the mode of all the operation modes (H_t^m), the specific HVAC system of the room doesn't work and doesn't consume energy. With these considerations, the temperature increment variable is constructed as:

$$\Delta T_t^r = \begin{cases} \widehat{T}_t^{i,r} - T_{t-1}^{i,r} & \text{if } (H_t^m < 3 \ \& \ H_t^{m,r} == H_t^m) \\ T_{t-1}^{i,r} - \widehat{T}_t^{i,r} & \text{if } (H_t^m > 2 \ \& \ H_t^{m,r} == H_t^m) \end{cases}$$

Also, by using the mode of the HVAC system's operation mode variable, it is possible to train two different models, one to predict the part of the energy used to heat the spaces (Φ_t^h) and another one to predict the energy used to cool the spaces (Φ_t^c). Since no power contribution should occur when the HVAC status ($\Phi_t^{st,r}$) is OFF, the relationship between the temperature increment (ΔT_t^r) for each room and the energy consumption can be linearised by multiplying these two variables. Finally, by combining the contributions of each space, the total HVAC energy consumption (Φ_t) can be modelled using an ARX approach. The resulting ARX model used to estimate the electricity consumption contribution of each space is the following:

$$\begin{cases} \gamma \Phi_t^h = \sum_{r=1}^R \beta_{1,r} (\Delta T_t^r \times \Phi_t^{st,r}) + \beta_h T^{b,h} + \beta_c T^{b,c} + \beta_n n^{hvac} + \epsilon_t \\ \gamma \Phi_t^c = \sum_{r=1}^R \beta_{1,r} (\Delta T_t^r \times \Phi_t^{st,r}) + \beta_h T^{b,h} + \beta_c T^{b,c} + \beta_n n^{hvac} + \epsilon_t \end{cases}$$

In this model, all the terms with the backward shift operator (B) are the autoregressive terms, while the others are the linear parameters. Regarding the autoregressive terms, they are defined as:

$$f(B) = 1 + f_1 B^1 \dots + f_n B^n$$

Where n is the number of lags, or order, of the backward shift operator B , obtaining the equivalent models for heating ($\widehat{\Phi}_t^h$) and cooling ($\widehat{\Phi}_t^c$) energies:

$$\begin{cases} \widehat{\Phi}_t^h = \beta_{0,t} + \sum_{r=1}^R \beta_{1,r,t} (\Delta T_t^r \times \Phi_t^{st,r}) + \beta_{h,t} T^{b,h} + \beta_{c,t} T^{b,c} + \beta_{n,t} n^{hvac} + \epsilon_t \\ \widehat{\Phi}_t^c = \beta_{0,t} + \sum_{r=1}^R \beta_{1,r,t} (\Delta T_t^r \times \Phi_t^{st,r}) + \beta_{h,t} T^{b,h} + \beta_{c,t} T^{b,c} + \beta_{n,t} n^{hvac} + \epsilon_t \end{cases}$$

As observed in the thermal models, the coefficients relating the input variables to the outputs are time-varying; this is because the training method used enables the model to adapt its coefficients when new data is available. The training method is described below.

The heating ($T^{b,h}$) and cooling ($T^{b,c}$) balance temperatures are used to add to the model the changes of the HVAC system's efficiency and the comfort indoor temperature that affect the energy consumption due to changes in the outdoor temperature. These variables are created because the relationship between energy consumption and outdoor temperature is nonlinear. While consumption increases during periods of more extreme outdoor temperatures (when heat or cold is higher), it decreases during periods with milder temperatures. To linearise these relations, the following expressions are used:

$$T_t^{b,h} = \begin{cases} T_t^{ref,h} - T_t^e & \text{if } (T_t^e < T_t^{ref,h} \ \& \ n_t^{hvac} > 0) \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases}$$

$$T_t^{b,c} = \begin{cases} T_t^e - T_t^{ref,c} & \text{if } (T_t^e > T_t^{ref,c} \ \& \ n_t^{hvac} > 0) \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases}$$

Also, it includes the condition that at least one machine should be working ($n_t^{hvac} > 0$) in order to only consider this variable when the HVACs are operating. The variables $T_t^{ref,h}$ and $T_t^{ref,c}$ are the heating and cooling reference temperatures, respectively, used as hyperparameters in the training process. This is done to identify reference temperatures that better explain the energy consumption behaviour. Their possible values are:

$$\begin{cases} T^{ref,h} = \text{sequence between 19 and 27 degrees C, by steps of 0,5 degrees C} \\ T^{ref,c} = \text{sequence between 0 and 19 degrees C, by steps of 0,5 degrees C} \end{cases}$$

Finally, the total consumption of the HVAC system is the combination of the results of both models:

$$\widehat{\Phi}_t = \widehat{\Phi}_t^h + \widehat{\Phi}_t^c$$

Model's nomenclature:

Φ_t = HVAC total energy consumption

$H_t^{m,r}$ = HVAC systems operation mode for the room r, possible status: 0-Hot_Water, 1-Heating, 2-Heating_Eco, 3-Anti_Freeze, 4-Cooling

$\Phi_t^{st,r}$ = HVAC systems status for the room r

$T^{b,h}$ = heating balance temperature

$T^{b,c}$ = cooling balance temperature

n^{hvac} = number of HVAC systems operating

$\widehat{T}_t^{i,r}$ = indoor temperature of the room r predicted by its thermal model

T^e = Raw outdoor temperature to consider fast changes in indoor temperatures due to changes in the daily minimum and maximum temperatures.

Φ_t^h = energy used to heat the spaces.

Φ_t^c = energy used to cool the spaces (Φ_t^c).

$T^{ref,h}$ = heating reference temperature

$T^{ref,c}$ = cooling reference temperature

ΔT^r = Temperature increment of the room r

Model inputs description:

For each room of the building, the following inputs are added:

- Increment of the room's temperature (ΔT_t^r) combined with the status of the room's HVAC system ($\Phi^{st,r}$). Used to consider the contribution of energy that is required to modify the temperature of the room when its HVAC system is operating.
- The heating ($T^{b,h}$) and cooling ($T^{b,c}$) balance temperatures. Used to add to the model the changes of the HVAC system's efficiency and the comfort indoor temperature that affect the energy consumption due to changes in the outdoor temperature.

Also, the following additional variables are included:

- An intercept term ($\beta_{0,t}$) to consider the baseload consumption of the HVAC central system.
- The number of HVAC systems operating (n^{hvac}) is considered for the baseload consumption of each room's HVAC systems when they are operating.
- Raw outdoor temperature ($T^{c,k}$) to consider the variation of the coefficient of performance of the boiler due to changes in the adjoining spaces' temperature.

Training function cost:

Since a machine learning model is used, the model's hyperparameters and coefficients must be obtained during training. During this process, a cost function must be chosen to evaluate performance. The cost function chosen for this model is the RMSE between the predicted and measured temperatures.

To track changes in the thermal behaviour of building rooms over time, the model is trained using a Recursive Least Squares (RLS) approach. This training approach is used to create an adaptive model, enabling continuous update of its coefficients as new data arrives. The objective during the training process is to minimise the cost function equation defined by:

$$J(\theta) = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda^{k-i} (y_i - \theta^\top x_i)^2$$

Where θ is the parameter vector to be estimated, y_i is the vector of observations, x_i is the vector of input variables, λ is the forgetting factor that determines the weight given to the past observations. By adjusting λ , the speed at which the model can adapt to the new data can be adjusted. Since the variation in building space behaviour, and consequently their thermal model behaviour, depends on their usage, the parameter λ can take different values depending on the studied room, and for different buildings, it can take different values depending on the studied room and for different buildings. For this reason, this parameter is included as a hyperparameter in the model, which is tuned during the training process.

In the RLS approach, the coefficients are calculated recursively. This approach consists of a Kalman filter with the model coefficients in the state vector. If only the 0 horizon is used, the coefficients are updated at each time step t by:

$$R_t = \lambda R_{t-1} + x_t x_t^\top$$

$$\theta_t = \theta_{t-1} + R_t^{-1} x_t (y_t - x_t^\top \theta_{t-1})$$

Stage 3: Non HVAC energy consumption estimation

This model is used to predict the energy consumption that is not related to the HVAC systems of each room. Since this consumption is not affected by the variables of the optimisation process, it doesn't need to be linear and is modelled based on calendar features. For this reason, a Random Forest (RF) approach is used to model this part of the consumption. The inputs of the model are:

- Hour of the day
- Day of the year
- Day of the week
- A variable indicating if the day is a holiday or not
- Number of operating HVAC

Training function cost:

Since a machine learning model is used, the model's hyperparameters and coefficients must be obtained during training. During this process, a cost function must be chosen to evaluate performance. The cost function chosen for this model is the RMSE between the predicted and measured temperatures.

Prediction Process

The prediction process consists of using the DT to predict the energy consumption. The models presented before are used to estimate each output by varying their input variables with the forecasted ones or the estimated ones by the optimisation process

The Prediction Process follows five stages:

Stage 1: Data update

The forecasts from the different APIs are combined with the optimisation process setpoints for the HVAC variables in order to feed the DT with the necessary data that will be in charge of predicting the new energy consumption. Since the model uses the previous 5 lags of the variables (5 previous states) as the initial state of the building's room, the measurements of the variables for these 5 previous states should be provided. The format of the input will then be like the following:

start	end	AmbTemp_1 (°C)	TempSP_1	PW_1	OpMode_1	outdoorTemperature (K)	WindSpeed (m/s)	...
First horizon of prediction - 5 hours	First horizon of prediction - 4 hours	24	22	1	3	25	3	...
...	
Last horizon of prediction	Last horizon of prediction +1 hour	22	22	1	3	26	3	...

The inputs required by the DT, which need to be included as columns of a dataframe, are the following:

Time variables columns:

- start: starting time of the sample (for a sample between 5:00 and 6:00, this variable will take a value of 5:00)
- end: ending time of the sample (for a sample between 5:00 and 6:00, this variable will take a value of 6:00)

Variables coming from the optimisation process:

For each room:

- OpMode: Operation mode of the HVAC of the HVAC system (named OpMode_r were r is the number that identifies the room)

- PW: Status of the HVAC system of the room (named PW_r, where r is the number that identifies the room)
- TempSP: HVAC system setpoint temperature of the room (named PW_r, where r is the number that identifies the room)
- AmbTemp: Ambient temperature of the room (named AmbTemp_r, where r is the number that identifies the room) in degC. This value is only required for the 5 previous lags. For the other sample times, they can be empty (NA).

Variables coming from the forecast process:

- airTemperature: outdoor temperature at the building location in kelvins. ([source: Meteogalicia](#))
- WindDir: wind direction at the building location.**
- WindSpeed: wind speed at the building location.**
- GHI: global horizontal irradiance at the building location. ([source: Meteogalicia](#))
- azimuth: solar azimuth angle at the building location. ([source: PVlib package from Python](#))
- elevation: solar elevation at the building location. ([source: PVlib package from Python](#))

**Instead of those on the first version, the u, v (east wind and north wind) components are acquired from Meteogalicia data, and they are transformed into wind speed and wind direction using trigonometry.

Stage 2: Room's temperature prediction

Predict the temperature of each room depending on the outdoor meteorological variables, the effect of the adjoining rooms, the internal gains and the HVAC system gain.

$$T_r = f(B(SP_r), B(T_r), B(T_o), B(T_{cs}), SP_{cs}, WF)$$

$B(SP_r)$ = regression series setpoint of the room temperature → **controllable input**

$B(T_r)$ = autoregression terms of the room temperature

$B(T_o)$ = regression series of the outdoor temperature

$B(T_c)$ = regression series of the previous adjoining spaces temperature. This regression uses only previous lags (starting at t-1) because the current temperatures are unknown.

SP_{cs} = actual setpoint of the adjoining spaces' temperature multiplied by their HVAC status

WF = weather features

Stage 3: HVAC energy consumption prediction using room temperatures, HVAC variables and weather features

The estimated temperature of each room is used to estimate the energy that the HVAC system must provide to go from the previous temperature to the new one for each room. The energy contributions required for each room are combined to obtain the total energy that the HVAC must provide. Also, outdoor meteorological variables and the previous values of the energy consumption are considered in the equation to assess its efficiency behaviour.

$$E = f\left(\sum_{r=1}^R ((T_t^{i,r} - T_{t-1}^{i,r}) \times HVAC^{st,r}), WF, N^{hvac}\right)$$

$T^{i,r}$ = internal temperature of room (r)

$HVAC^{st,r}$ = status of the HVAC system of room (r)

WF = weather features

N^{hvac} = number of HVAC systems operating

Stage 4: Non HVAC energy consumption prediction

Since there are different readings on total energy consumption and HVAC system energy, the HVAC energy can be subtracted from the total consumption to determine the energy used by other systems, such as lighting and computers. Given that there is no information available regarding the usage of these other systems, a calendar-based model will be utilised to estimate this portion of the building's energy consumption, especially considering it is a tertiary building. year.

$$E = f(CF, n^{hvac}, T^e)$$

CF = calendar features

n^{hvac} = number of HVAC systems operating

T^e = outdoor temperature

Stage 5: Return the information to the optimisation

In this stage, the sum of non-HVAC and HVAC energy prediction is returned to the optimisation process in order to be able to take the next decision.

Dynamics Estimation Process

The dynamics estimation process follows three stages:

Stage 1: Data update

The forecasts from the different APIs are combined with the building's monitored variables, which are used as inputs to the model. Since the model uses the previous 5 lags of the variables (5 previous states) as the initial state of the building's room, measurements of these variables for those 5 previous states should be provided. The format of the input will then be like the following:

start	end	AmbTemp_1 (°C)	PW_1	OpMode_1	outdoorTemperature (k)	WindSpeed (m/s)	...
First horizon of required inputs transformations - 5 hours	First horizon of prediction - 4 hours	24	1	3	25	3	...
...	
Last horizon of required inputs transformations	Last horizon of prediction +1 hour	22	1	3	26	3	...

The inputs required by the DT, which need to be included as columns of a dataframe, are the following:

Time variables columns:

- start: starting time of the sample (for a sample between 5:00 and 6:00, this variable will take a value of 5:00)
- end: ending time of the sample (for a sample between 5:00 and 6:00, this variable will take a value of 6:00)

Variables coming from the optimisation process:

For each room:

- OpMode: Operation mode of the HVAC of the HVAC system (named OpMode_r, where r is the number that identifies the room)
- PW: Status of the HVAC system of the room (named PW_r, where r is the number that identifies the room)
- AmbTemp: Ambient temperature of the room (named AmbTemp_r, where r is the number that identifies the room) in degC. This value is only required for the 5 previous lags. For the other sample times, they can be empty (NA).

Variables coming from the forecast process:

- airTemperature: outdoor temperature at the building location in kelvins. ([source: Meteogalicia](#))

- WindDir: wind direction at the building location.**
- WindSpeed: wind speed at the building location.**
- GHI: global horizontal irradiance at the building location. ([source: Meteogalicia](#))
- azimuth: solar azimuth angle at the building location. ([source: PVlib package from Python](#))
- elevation: solar elevation at the building location. ([source: PVlib package from Python](#))

**instead of that ones on the first version the u, v (east wind and north wind) components are acquired from Meteogalicia data and they are transformed into wind speed and wind direction using trigonometry.

Stage 2: Estimation of the coefficient matrix and the transformed inputs for the room temperature models.

This process builds a matrix corresponding to the cooling and heating temperature model coefficients for each room. For each room, the coefficients are the ones relating the output to each input as defined in the model presented in the training process section, given by:

$$\widehat{T}_t^{i,r} = \sum_{l=1}^L \phi_{l,t} T_{t-l}^{i,r} + \sum_{n=0}^N \gamma_{n,t} T_{t-n}^{sp,r} + \sum_{r=0}^R \omega_{elp,r,t} T_{t-r}^{e,lp} + \sum_{k=1}^K \beta_{k,t} T_t^{sp,k} + \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{p=1}^P \omega_{c,k,p,t} T_{t-p}^{c,k} + \omega_{i,t} (W_t^{s,lp} \times W_t^{d,fs} \times \Psi_t) + \omega_{s,t} (I_t^{sol,lp} \times S_t^{az,fs} \times S_t^{el,fs}) + \epsilon_t$$

Where the coefficients correspond with ϕ_l , γ_n , $\omega_{elp,r}$, β_k , $\omega_{c,k,p}$, ω_i and ω_s

Also, the transformed inputs for all terms in the equation are estimated..

The coefficient matrix nomenclature is the following:

There are coefficients that affect only some specific rooms' dynamics:

- The internal temperature of each room is named AmbTemp_r, where r denotes the number that identifies the room. For example, for room 1, it's named AmbTemp_1.
- Each lag of the internal temperature of the room added to the model is named AmbTemp_r_lk, where r denotes the number that identifies the room and k the lag. For example, lag 1 of the temperature for room 1 is named AmbTemp_1_l1 and the second lag AmbTemp_1_l2.
- The setpoint temperatures of the HVAC system of each room are named TempSP_r_l1, where r denotes the number that identifies the room. For example, for room 1, it's named TempSP_1.
- Each lag of the setpoint temperatures of the HVAC system of each room is named TempSP_r_lk, where r denotes the number that identifies the room and k the lag. For

example, lag 1 of the setpoint temperature for the room's 1 HVAC system is named TempSP_1_l1 and the second lag TempSP_1_l1 .

- Each of the component of the wind speed ($W^{s,lp}$), interacting with Fourier series of the wind direction ($W^{d,fs}$) and the temperature difference between room's indoors and outdoors ($\Psi = T^{i,r} - T^e$) are named "wcos1_r", "wsin1_r", "wcos2_r", "wsin2_r" (two firsts FS sinus and cosinus coefficients), where r denotes the number that identifies the room that is affected by these coefficients. For example, for the room 1, FS coefficients are named "wcos1_1", "wsin1_1", "wcos2_1", "wsin2_1"

Also, there are some coefficients that affect all the rooms, such as:

- The Solar direct normal irradiance ($I^{sol,lp}$), interacting with the Fourier series of the solar azimuth ($S^{az,fs}$) and of the solar elevation ($S^{el,fs}$) coefficients are named "scos1", "ssin1", "scos2", "ssin2" (two firsts FS sinus and cosinus coefficients)
- The external temperature of the building coefficients is named outdoorTemperature and its lags are named "outdoorTemperature_l1", "outdoorTemperature_l2", "outdoorTemperature_l3", "outdoorTemperature_l4", "outdoorTemperature_l5"

This information is later used by the optimisation process in order to build the dynamical models of the system by constructing the state equations, used to represent the dynamics of the system, given by:

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{x}(t) &= \mathbf{A}x(t) + \mathbf{B}u(t) \\ y(t) &= \mathbf{C}x(t) + \mathbf{D}u(t)\end{aligned}$$

Where \dot{x} is the state vector, y is the output vector, u is the control vector. On the other hand, A is the state matrix, B is the input matrix, C is the output matrix, and D is the feedforward matrix.

Stage 3: Estimation of the coefficient matrix and the transformed inputs for HVAC energy consumption models.

This process builds a matrix corresponding to the cooling and heating HVAC energy consumption model coefficients for each room. These coefficients are the ones relating the output (energy consumption) with each input (predictor) as defined in the model presented in the training process section, given by:

$$\begin{cases} \widehat{\Phi}_t^h = \beta_{0,t} + \sum_{r=1}^R \beta_{1,r,t} (\Delta T_t^r \times \Phi_t^{st,r}) + \beta_{h,t} T^{b,h} + \beta_{c,t} T^{b,c} + \beta_{n,t} n^{hvac} + \epsilon_t \\ \widehat{\Phi}_t^c = \beta_{0,t} + \sum_{r=1}^R \beta_{1,r,t} (\Delta T_t^r \times \Phi_t^{st,r}) + \beta_{h,t} T^{b,h} + \beta_{c,t} T^{b,c} + \beta_{n,t} n^{hvac} + \epsilon_t \end{cases}$$

Where the coefficients correspond with β_0 , $\beta_{1,r}$, β_h , β_c and β_n

Also, the transformed inputs corresponding to all the terms used in the equation are estimated.

The coefficient matrix nomenclature is the following:

- The temperature increment of each room is named IncTemp_r, where r denotes the number that identifies the room. For example, for room 1, it's named IncTemp_1.
- The heating ($T^{b,h}$) and cooling ($T^{b,c}$) balance temperatures are expressed in the matrix names as ComfTempHeating and ComfTempCooling
- The intercept term is named the intercept in the matrix.
- The number of HVAC systems operating (n^{hvac}) is named nhvac in the coefficients matrix.

This information is also used later by the optimisation process in order to build the dynamical models of the system by constructing the space state equations, used to represent the dynamics of the system, given by:

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{x}(t) &= \mathbf{A}x(t) + \mathbf{B}u(t) \\ y(t) &= \mathbf{C}x(t) + \mathbf{D}u(t)\end{aligned}$$

Where \dot{x} is the state vector, y is the output vector, u is the control vector. On the other hand, A is the state matrix, B is the input matrix, C is the output matrix, and D is the feedforward matrix.

Stage 3: Non HVAC energy consumption prediction

Since there are separate lectures on total energy consumption and HVAC system energy, the HVAC energy can be subtracted from the total consumption to determine the energy used by other systems, such as lighting and computers. Given that there is no information available regarding the usage of these other systems, a calendar-based model will be utilised to estimate this portion of the building's energy consumption, especially considering it is a tertiary building. year.

$$E = f(CF, n^{hvac}, T^e)$$

CF = calendar features

n^{hvac} = number of HVAC systems operating

T^e = outdoor temperature

The optimisation process needs this information in order to complement the HVAC energy consumption component and be informed about the overall consumption of the building in each step. In this way, it can optimise the building assets in each timestep.

Stage 4: Return the information to the optimisation

The information is returned to the optimisation process using a JSON format. The JSON file contains the following elements:

- **TransformedInputsTemperature:** a dataframe with the transformations (excluding the ones of setpoint temperatures, which are estimated by the optimisation process) of the inputs of the temperature models (can be used for both heating and cooling).
- **CoefsTempHeating:** matrix with the temperature heating model coefficients that give the dynamics of the temperature model when it's in heating mode. This matrix includes the relations between each room's temperature and the inputs of the temperature heating model, including the exogenous inputs (u) and their autoregressive terms ($x-k$).
- **CoefsTempHeatingColNames:** column names of the CoefsTempHeating matrix (ordered in the same way as the columns of the matrix), in order to know how columns are ordered.
- **CoefsTempHeatingRowNames:** row names of the CoefsTempHeating matrix (ordered in the same way as the rows of the matrix), in order to know how rows are ordered.
- **CoefsTempCooling:** matrix with the temperature cooling model coefficients that give the dynamics of the temperature model when it's in cooling mode. This matrix includes the relations between each room's temperature and the inputs of the temperature cooling model, including the exogenous inputs (u) and their autoregressive terms ($x-k$).
- **CoefsTempCoolingColNames:** column names of the CoefsTempCooling matrix (ordered in the same way as the columns of the matrix) in order to know how columns are ordered.
- **CoefsTempCoolingRowNames:** row names of the CoefsTempCooling matrix (ordered in the same way as the rows of the matrix) in order to know how rows are ordered.
- **CoefsHVACEnergyHeating:** matrix with the HVAC energy heating model coefficients that give the dynamics of the energy model when it's in heating mode. This matrix includes the relations between the HVAC energy consumption and the inputs of its cooling model and heating model, including the exogenous inputs (u) and their autoregressive terms ($x-k$).
- **CoefsHVACEnergyHeating:** matrix with HVAC energy heating model coefficients that give the dynamics of the energy model when it's in heating mode. This matrix includes the relations between the HVAC energy consumption and the inputs of its cooling model, including the exogenous inputs (u) and their autoregressive terms ($x-k$).
- **CoefsHVACEnergyHeatingColNames:** column names of the CoefsHVACEnergyHeating matrix (ordered in the same way as the columns of the matrix) in order to know how columns are ordered.
- **CoefsHVACEnergyHeatingRowNames:** row names of the CoefsHVACEnergyHeating matrix (ordered in the same way as the rows of the matrix), in order to know how rows are ordered.
- **CoefsHVACEnergyCooling:** matrix with HVAC energy cooling model coefficients that give the dynamics of the energy model when it's in cooling mode. This matrix includes the

relations between the HVAC energy consumption and the inputs of its cooling model, including the exogenous inputs (u) and their autoregressive terms ($x-k$).

- **CoefsHVACEnergyCoolingColNames:** column names of the CoefsHVACEnergyCooling matrix (ordered in the same way as the columns of the matrix) in order to know how columns are ordered.
- **CoefsHVACEnergyCoolingRowNames:** row names of the CoefsHVACEnergyCooling matrix (ordered in the same way as the rows of the matrix), in order to know how rows are ordered.
- **NonHVACEnergyPredicted:** dataframe with the predictions of the NON HVAC component of the energy consumption. This dataframe only includes the energy prediction and the time variables for the time period that is introduced at the input.

Results

Rooms thermal models results:

Since the models (heating and cooling) are trained only when the status of the HVAC of the specific room that is being modelled is ON, only these temperatures are modelled and predicted. The following graphs show the results of three rooms on different building floors as an example:

The results for the complete period:

Room 1:

Room 20:

The results for the complete period:

Room 98:

The results for the complete period:

As the model is trained using an RLS method, the coefficients evolve over time. Considering this, it makes no sense to divide them into training and validation periods, since the coefficients for the two periods will differ. To evaluate the model results, metrics are computed using the validation period, the last 90 days (approximately 3 months) of the sampling period. Also, as can be seen in the previous images, the errors at the beginning of the period are much higher than those at the end. This is because, since this training method updates the coefficients continuously with the new data, at the beginning, the coefficients are trained with only a few samples. Over time, they keep updating using the new data, and the results keep improving. The next images show the validation periods of the temperature model of the rooms used as an example:

Room 1

The results for the validation period are used to obtain the metrics of the model:

Room 20

The results for the validation period are used to obtain the metrics of the model:

Room 20

The results for the validation period are used to obtain the metrics of the model:

The metrics used to evaluate the models are the Mean Absolute Error (MAE), the Mean Squared Root Error (RMSE), the CVMSE and the determination factor (R^2). It must be noted that the thermal model output is the temperature of each room in kelvins, which must be considered in evaluating the metrics. The following table shows the metrics for the temperature model of each room of the building:

Results metrics for the thermal model

	MAE_heating	MAE_cooling	RMSE_heating	RMSE_cooling	CVRMSE_heating	CVRMSE_cooling	R2_heating	R2_cooling
Room_1	0.749	0.4746	1.0611	0.6321	0.0036	0.0021	0.6715	0.8316
Room_2	0.6334	0.3416	0.8452	0.4686	0.0029	0.0016	0.8291	0.8102
Room_3	0.9234	0.3088	1.2903	0.4559	0.0044	0.0015	0.7974	0.8549
Room_4	0.7815	0.2573	1.0806	0.3614	0.0037	0.0012	0.7815	0.8978
Room_5	0.7212	0.3294	0.9993	0.4322	0.0034	0.0015	0.8237	0.8206
Room_6	0.3852	0.2796	0.5089	0.3853	0.0017	0.0013	0.91	0.8206
Room_7	0.3785	0.4286	0.5175	0.558	0.0018	0.0019	0.9065	0.8598
Room_8	0.3624	0.1655	0.4947	0.2305	0.0017	8e-04	0.9193	0.978
Room_9	0.5718	0.4088	0.7655	0.8272	0.0026	0.0028	0.8517	0.7395
Room_10	1.1137	0.7907	1.493	1.119	0.0051	0.0038	0.7436	0.6562
Room_11	0.9198	0.7008	1.226	0.9313	0.0041	0.0031	0.7087	0.641
Room_12	0.3318	0.1736	0.4349	0.2419	0.0015	8e-04	0.9019	0.9254
Room_13	0.8339	0.7061	1.2832	0.9014	0.0043	0.0031	0.8767	0.4403
Room_14	0.5102	0.3457	0.7223	0.456	0.0025	0.0015	0.8608	0.9092
Room_15	0.8028	0.4507	1.105	0.641	0.0037	0.0022	0.5998	0.6835
Room_16	0.8638	0.4967	1.2684	0.6511	0.0043	0.0022	0.6112	0.7331
Room_17	0.9738	0.5991	1.3775	0.8872	0.0047	0.003	0.3882	0.514
Room_18	0.395	0.1579	0.5753	0.2278	0.002	8e-04	0.9002	0.9667
Room_19	0.742	0.4656	1.1038	0.6416	0.0037	0.0022	0.7882	0.693
Room_20	1.1075	0.4085	1.5159	0.6903	0.0051	0.0023	0.6186	0.7546
Room_21	0.8756	0.2839	1.1799	0.445	0.004	0.0015	0.773	0.8333
Room_23	0.9114	0.5331	1.2704	0.71	0.0043	0.0024	0.4641	0.7069
Room_24	0.4118	0.3563	0.5514	0.4898	0.0019	0.0016	0.8954	0.9399
Room_25	0.7008	0.8221	0.9817	1.0994	0.0033	0.0037	0.7795	0.6077
Room_26	0.8702	0.732	1.2135	1.0077	0.0041	0.0034	0.5724	0.6418
Room_27	0.8564	0.8819	1.1981	1.1975	0.0041	0.004	0.7848	0.485
Room_28	0.4893	0.2336	0.6728	0.3492	0.0023	0.0012	0.5355	0.8851
Room_29	0.6908	0.4761	0.9897	0.6622	0.0034	0.0022	0.5026	0.487
Room_30	0.2916	0.2575	0.3855	0.3618	0.0013	0.0012	0.9374	0.9021
Room_76	0.5689	0.3832	0.8278	0.5333	0.0028	0.0018	0.7247	0.9429
Room_77	0.4398	0.4707	0.6556	0.6968	0.0022	0.0024	0.8278	0.7279
Room_78	0.6908	0.3984	0.9599	0.6961	0.0032	0.0023	0.7201	0.9055
Room_79	0.6235	0.4835	0.9646	0.7548	0.0033	0.0025	0.633	0.8807
Room_80	0.4728	0.3815	0.7714	0.7406	0.0026	0.0025	0.7796	0.891
Room_97	0.6693	0.2437	8.367	0.4474	0.0285	0.0015	0.0132	0.8347
Room_98	0.4985	0.2875	0.8447	0.4626	0.0029	0.0016	0.8694	0.8738

The average value for each metric is the following:

For the heating model:

- MAE in evaluation period = 0,6712
- RMSE in evaluation period = 1,1528
- CVRMSE in evaluation period = 0,003917
- R^2 in evaluation period = 0,7306

For the cooling model:

- MAE in evaluation period = 0,4310

- RMSE in evaluation period = 0,6221
- CVRMSE in evaluation period = 0,002097
- R^2 in evaluation period = 0,7799

Finally, a boxplot for each of the metrics is also used to show the statistical distribution of the metrics obtained for each room model:

HVAC energy model results:

Predicted versus measured energy consumption for the complete period:

Predicted versus measured energy consumption for the validation period of the year 2025:

The metrics used to evaluate the models are the Mean Absolute Error (MAE), the Mean Squared Root Error (RMSE), the CVRMSE and the determination factor (R^2). The validation period statistical indicators are the following:

For the heating model:

- MAE in evaluation period = 315,8775

- RMSE in evaluation period = 801,371
- CVRMSE in evaluation period = 0,8464352
- R^2 in evaluation period = 0,6906897

For the cooling model:

- MAE in evaluation period = 1316,283
- RMSE in evaluation period = 1819,407
- CVRMSE in evaluation period = 0,2105761
- R^2 in evaluation period = 0,9774884

Non-HVAC energy model results:

Predicted versus measured energy consumption for the complete period:

Predicted versus measured energy consumption for the validation period of the year 2025:

The metrics used to evaluate the models are the Mean Absolute Error (MAE), the Mean Squared Root Error (RMSE), the CVRMSE and the determination factor (R^2). The validation period statistical indicators are the following:

- MAE in evaluation period = 1478,537
- RMSE in evaluation period = 2192,992
- CVRMSE in evaluation period = 0,3060992
- R^2 in evaluation period = 0,8862816